

inDICES

Measuring the Impact of Digital Culture

Deliverable 2.4

Evaluative assessment of the impact of the EU Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market in the cultural heritage sector

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the activities carried out during the last year of the inDICEs project within Work Package 2. It presents a framework for assessing the impact of legal and policy instruments in the cultural heritage sector, and applies this evaluative framework to the relevant provisions of the new European Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market. Deliverable D2.4. departs from the results obtained in Project inDICEs, and presents a thorough theoretical evaluation of the new Directive, relying on authoritative literary sources, complemented by input from advocacy groups and other legal research projects focused on the cultural heritage sector (such as Project ReCreating Europe).

2 Introduction and Objectives

In May 2015, the European Commission, at the time presided by politician Jean-Claude Juncker, unveiled the European Strategy for a Digital Single Market¹, a complex policy plan aimed at adapting the EU's Single market to the digital age by promoting better online access to digital goods and services, stimulating cross-border e-commerce within the European space, and modernizing the rules applicable to the audio-visual, cultural and communication sectors², thus ensuring that the European economy could take full advantages of the opportunities that the digital era had to offer.

The European Strategy for a European Digital Single Market

The European Commission Communication on the Digital Single Market strategy for Europe establishes three primary goals : (1) to better online access for consumers and businesses across Europe, (2) to create the right conditions for the development of advanced digital networks and innovative services, and (3) to maximize the growth potential of the Digital Economy .

According to Objective 2.4. of the Communication, copyright underpins creativity and the cultural industry in Europe. It also reveals that “56% of Europeans use the internet for cultural purposes” . Regardless of this high level of consumption, cross-border unavailability of digital content is a persistent problem, a fact that “is partly linked to the territoriality of copyright and difficulties associated with the clearing of rights.” . Considering this global trend toward digitization, Europe needs a more harmonised copyright regime that can provide incentives to create and invest while “allowing transmission and consumption of content across borders, building on our rich cultural diversity” . The Commission solidifies the intention to draft future legislative proposals to reduce the differences between national copyright regimes, allowing for wider online access to works by users across the EU. It would, in turn, foster “greater legal certainty for the cross-border use of content for specific purposes (e.g. research, education, text and data mining, etc.)” .

Towards a modern, more European copyright framework

This particular policy objective would soon merit an independent Communication from the Commission (COM[2015] 626), titled “Towards a modern, more European copyright framework” released on 9 December 2015. According to this second Communication, the objectives of ensuring wide availability of creative content across the EU while providing a high level of protection for right holders, and the maintenance of a good balance with other public policy goals, like education and research, “play an important part in Europe’s economic and societal progress, international

¹ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe, COM/2015/0192.

² Section 2.4. Better access to digital content - A modern, more European copyright framework. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe, COM/2015/0192.

competitiveness and cultural diversity”³. These objectives can only be achieved by establishing a higher level of harmonisation into the current EU copyright rules, particularly by “addressing aspects related to the territoriality of copyright” and adapting copyright rules to “new technological realities so that the rules continue to meet their objectives.”.

As a means to take this plan into action, the European Commission stated their intention to consider legislative proposals on EU exceptions to increase the level of harmonisation by “spring 2016”. As such, the arrival of the Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on copyright in the Digital Single Market (COM/2016/0593 – 2016/0290), in September 2016, did not come as a surprise. The proposal was received with criticism by national representatives⁴, as well as the public⁵, and was debated in Parliament in 2018 until an updated position of the European Parliament was approved. Trilogue negotiations took place in 2019⁶ until, at last, the Directive would face approval by the Council of the European Union, entering into force on 7 June 2019⁷, with a 2-year deadline for Member-States to transpose it to their national laws.

Directive 2019/790 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market

The final text of Directive 2019/790 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market (commonly abbreviated as the CDSM Directive, or simply DSM Directive) includes 86 Recitals and 32 Articles, divided into five main titles. According to the Recitals of the Directive, and in line with the strategy defined in the aforementioned Communications, the CDSM Directive puts forward several essential goals:

- provide for a high but balanced level of protection for rightsholders (Recitals 2 and 6),
- respect and promote cultural diversity (Recital 2),

³ Section 1. Copyright in the digital single market. COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS: Towards a modern, more European copyright framework COM(2015) 626 final.

⁴ João Pedro Quintais, The New Copyright Directive: A tour d’horizon – Part I (2019), Kluwer Copyright Blog <<http://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2019/06/07/the-new-copyright-directive-a-tour-dhorizon-part-i/>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁵ Several public demonstrations occurred in 2019, most notably protesting against the implementation of Article 17 (formerly Article 13). “For two years, internet communities have debated European copyright reform, whose opponents have been dismissed as bots by German conservative MEP Sven Schulze. Protesters were there to prove they were real, in the first Europe-wide street demonstrations against internet regulation – voicing their opposition to specific sections of a new law, which the European Parliament could vote into legislation on March 26.”. Morgan Meaker, Inside the giant German protest trying to bring down Article 13: Article 17 (formerly Article 13) could become law this week. In Germany, protestors beg to differ (2019), Wired UK, <<https://www.wired.co.uk/article/article-13-protests>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁶ Alastair Shaw, Anne Schmitt, Penelope Thornton and Wesley Horion, DSM Watch: Crunch Time For The Copyright Directive (2019), Hogan Lovells Engage, <<https://www.engage.hoganlovells.com/knowledgeservices/news/dsm-watch-crunch-time-for-the-copyright-directive>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁷ Article 26(1) (Application in time) of Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC: “This Directive shall apply in respect of all works and other subject matter that are protected by national law in the field of copyright on or after 7 June 2021.”.

- adapt copyright legislation to technological developments and new business models (Recital 3),
- adapt certain exceptions and limitations to digital and cross-border environments (Recital 3),
- set rules for news publishers and online service providers storing and giving access to user-uploaded content (Recital 3),
- increase transparency and fairness in authors' and performers' contracts and remuneration (Recital 3), and
- foster the fields of research, innovation, education and preservation of cultural heritage through digital technologies (Recital 5).

As a way to achieve these goals, the Directive introduces a set of mandatory⁸ exceptions for research, educational and cultural heritage preservation purposes (Title II - Measures to adapt exceptions and limitations to the digital and cross-border environment), two new licensing mechanisms based on the presumed representativity of collective management organizations along with a ban on certain exclusive rights over public domain works (Title III – Measures to improve licensing practices and ensure wider access to content), a set of rights and obligations for publishers of press publications and online content-sharing service providers, as well as some mechanisms to ensure appropriate remuneration and contractual transparency for authors and performers (Title IV – Measures to achieve a well-functioning marketplace for copyright). The remaining sections, Title I and Title V, are respectively dedicated to defining the scope and terminology of the Directive and providing guidance on the relationship of the CDSM Directive with prior legal text.

Preservation and promotion of European Cultural Heritage

As evidenced by the objectives outlined in the Strategy for a Digital Single Market, the Communication “Towards a modern, more European copyright framework” and the above-mentioned text of Recitals 2 and 3 of the DSM Directive, the preservation of and promotion of access to European Cultural Heritage is one of the priorities in the development of new copyright legislation, with Cultural Heritage Institutions being part of a select group of beneficiaries. These institutions and the rules they may benefit (or not) from are the focal point of the present document.

The goal of the inDICEs project is to empower policymakers and decision-makers in the Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) to fully understand the social economic impact of digitization in their sectors. To do so, these policy and decision makers need to be fully aware of the impact of copyright rules on their activities. The previous Deliverables have briefly touched upon the updates to the copyright acquis brought by the DSM Directive by describing the new provisions. The goal of the present Deliverable is to further scrutinize them from a critical perspective, providing an evaluative assessment of the positive or negative impact of the new provisions introduced by the DSM Directive on the scope of activity of Cultural Heritage Institutions, which will be both the starting point and the core focal point of this analysis.

Scope and objectives of the evaluative approach

⁸ Caterina Sganga, A new era for EU copyright exceptions and limitations? Judicial flexibility and legislative discretion in the aftermath of the CDSM Directive and the trio of the Grand Chamber of the CJEU (2020) ERA Forum 21(2) 311-339, <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12027-020-00623-9>> accessed 14 November 2022.

This analysis is aimed at providing policy and policymakers, cultural heritage institution personnel, researchers, and the general public with a critical outlook on how the novel provisions complement or not the activities of a particular sector. It is a subjective analysis inclined towards the interests of the cultural sector, and reflective of how the sector may thrive within the new framework. It is not a practical guide for the concrete application of the provisions on everyday scenarios, nor is it a handbook for optimal implementation of the provisions for national lawmakers.

With the exception of the preceding Executive Summary, the present Introductory Chapter, and the final Conclusive Chapter, this deliverable is divided into 4 substantial chapters: Chapter 3 is dedicated to producing a set of criteria for the evaluation of the appropriateness of the provisions of the DSM Directive in the context of the activities of CHIs; Chapters 4, 5 and 6 are dedicated to applying the predeveloped evaluative matrix to the DSM Directive provisions of Title II, Title III and Title IV, respectively. Each chapter is introduced by a comprehensive recap of the Title's articles and an explanation of the choice of provisions considered to be relevant for the activity of CHI's.

The prior paragraph has made it clear that two Titles (of the DSM Directive), Title I and Title V, have not been assigned independent chapters. This should not be considered to be a disregard for the importance of the provisions contained therein, but rather a statement on their overall relevance for the entire analysis.

Title I is composed of two Articles, Article 1, defining the scope of the Directive⁹, and Article 2 providing some legal definitions of the terminology deployed in the legal instrument. As such, Article 2(3), for example, which defines "cultural heritage institution" as a publicly accessible library, museum, archive, or film/audio heritage institution, will not have the evaluative matrix applied to it as it contains no normative character, but rather a definition that will be helpful in understanding the normative range of the other provisions. This means that the content of Title I will not be "evaluated" as it provides no new rules¹⁰ that can bolster or hamper the activity of CHI's, but rather be used as a complement to the analysis of the other Titles that do contain prescriptive components.

The same reasoning applies to the final/transitory provisions in Title V. This Title contains 9 Articles, the majority of them about the relationship of the DSM Directive with other Directives (amendments and compatibility)¹¹, along with other procedural dispositions (application in time, transposition deadline, entry into force, etc.)¹². Within this Title, Article 25 would be, for the purposes of the

⁹ Article 1 (Subject matter and scope): 1. This Directive lays down rules which aim to harmonise further Union law applicable to copyright and related rights in the framework of the internal market, taking into account, in particular, digital and cross-border uses of protected content. It also lays down rules on exceptions and limitations to copyright and related rights, on the facilitation of licences, as well as rules which aim to ensure a well-functioning marketplace for the exploitation of works and other subject matter.

¹⁰ The provisions of Title I are essentially non-autonomous norms of the explanatory kind, as they directly relate or introduce other concepts but are themselves non-prescriptive in nature. To read more about the value-norm-fact trichotomy: María José Falcon y Tella, *A Three-Dimensional Theory of Law* (Koninklijke Brill 2010).

¹¹ Article 24 (Amendments to Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC) and Article 25 (Relationship with exceptions and limitations provided for in other directives).

¹² Article 26 (Application in time), Article 27 (Transitional provision), Article 28 (Protection of personal data), Article 29 (Transposition), Article 30 (Review), Article 31 (Entry into force), Article 32 (Addressees).

assessment hereby conducted, the most relevant one, as it provides Member States with a margin of flexibility (and even creativity) on the implementation of the DSM Directive¹³, allowing these Member States to adopt broader provisions, as long as these are compatible with the exceptions and limitations of the Database Directive¹⁴ and the InfoSoc Directive¹⁵, and relate to the fields/uses covered by the exceptions in the DSM Directive. This means that if a Member-State wanted to transpose a provision of the DSM Directive but enlarge its scope to fit with the nation's political objectives or legal history, they could, as long as this enlargement is deemed compatible with the previous copyright Directives and the objectives of the DSM Directive.

For example, and as later will be explained in greater detail, the cross-border education exception introduced by the DSM Directive does not include CHIs as beneficiaries of the exception. When conducting an assessment of the "CHI-appropriateness" of this provision, it is crucial to reflect on the mechanism of Article 25, which cannot be considered in isolation, and thus take into consideration the fact that this provision on educational exceptions, albeit limiting to cultural diversity in its literal form, could be enhanced by Article 25 due to the fact that Article 5(3)(a) of the InfoSoc Directive¹⁶ (a non-mandatory exception on illustration for teaching and scientific research) does not preclude CHIs as beneficiaries of the provision. This is the case since an activity-based approach is taken, instead of an institution-based one¹⁷. Of course, this mechanism can only be used in the transposition stage by the Member States, meaning it yields no material effects unless the national legislator chooses to make use of it. Nonetheless, a concrete and complete evaluation of the positive/negative net potential of a provision can only be achieved by addressing its potential range, and whether its scope could be enlarged by Article 25 or not.

¹³ Article 25 (Relationship with exceptions and limitations provided for in other directives) - Member States may adopt or maintain in force broader provisions, compatible with the exceptions and limitations provided for in Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC, for uses or fields covered by the exceptions or limitations provided for in this Directive.

¹⁴ Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases.

¹⁵ Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society.

¹⁶ "Member States may provide for exceptions or limitations to the rights provided for in Articles 2 and 3 in the following cases: (a) use for the sole purpose of illustration for teaching or scientific research, as long as the source, including the author's name, is indicated, unless this turns out to be impossible and to the extent justified by the non-commercial purpose to be achieved;"

¹⁷ Ana Lazarova, *The EU Copyright Reform's great disservice to free use for educational purposes* (2021), *Europeana Pro* <<https://pro.europeana.eu/post/the-eu-copyright-reform-s-great-disservice-to-free-use-for-educational-purposes>> accessed 14 November 2022.

3 Evaluative Framework

3.1 Introduction

As previously mentioned, the goal of the present document is to provide an evaluation of the provisions introduced by the new CDSM Directive based on their positive or negative effect on the establishment and development of the activities of CHIs in the Digital Single Market. Provisions deemed relevant for the objectives of CHIs are carefully scrutinized under the lens of the Evaluative Matrix, a framework composed of assessment criteria designed for this task.

The objectives of Cultural Heritage Institutions are many: to provide the public with access to cultural goods¹⁸, to preserve such goods in an optimal way as to allow future generations to retain access to them¹⁹, to educate the public, allowing them to learn from historical texts, artworks, and artifacts²⁰, to promote artistic and creative freedom²¹ and to provide support and foster scientific progress²², among many others.

To compose a matrix based on the myriad interests of CHIs alone would be a unilateral response to the objectives of the sector since the rules by which institutions play are defined by policymakers and legislators when considering not only the sector-specific interests, but also the interests of all involved parties. As the Communication “Towards a modern, more European copyright framework” expounds, one of the core objectives of the Strategy for a Digital Single Market is to balance all public policy interests, among them the promotion and protection of cultural activity and heritage, with a high level of protection for rightsholders, creating a level playing field for the use and exploitation of protected subject matter.

Considering that the protection and promotion of cultural heritage and diversity is one of the goals of the Directive, an effective approach to these goals is to focus on how the legal instrument intends to achieve them. Therefore, rather than arbitrarily picking a set of criteria based on an independent perception of the interests of CHI’s, the Evaluative Matrix departs from the sectoral interests that the Directive self-determines and proposes to pursue and safeguard.

As such, the first step in the crafting of this Evaluative Matrix is to identify these self-determined policy interests. After identifying the cultural policy objectives, the application of this general

¹⁸ European Parliament Report - A8-0207/2015: Report towards an integrated approach to cultural heritage for Europe, Committee on Culture and Education.

¹⁹ European Parliament Report - A8-0207/2015: Report towards an integrated approach to cultural heritage for Europe, Committee on Culture and Education.

²⁰ Cristiana Achille & Fausta Fiorillo, Teaching and Learning of Cultural Heritage: Engaging Education, Professional Training, and Experimental Activities (2022), *Heritage* 2022(5), 2565–2593, <<https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage5030134>> accessed 14 November 2022.

²¹ UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions, 5 June 2007, No. 43977.

²² European Parliament Report - A8-0207/2015: Report towards an integrated approach to cultural heritage for Europe, Committee on Culture and Education.

evaluative matrix to each provision of the Directive allows for the extraction of conclusions on how successfully or not the text of the legal instrument adheres to its self-determined goals.

3.2. Policy objectives for the cultural sector

The general rationales supporting legislative intervention and the enactment of the CDSM Directive can be found in Recitals 2 and 3 of the Directive²³. These are:

- To harmonize the copyright legal framework.
- To respect and promote cultural diversity.
- To address uncertainties caused by technological advancement so that relevant legislation does not restrict such progress.
- To adapt exceptions and limitations to cross-border environments.
- To set new rules for news publishers and online content-sharing service providers.
- To increase transparency and fairness in authors' and performers' contracts.
- To guarantee fairness in the marketplace.
- To provide for a high but balanced level of protection for rightsholders.

Through a careful consideration of the policy objectives that define the scope of action of the CDSM Directive, it is possible to conclude that some are more connected to the activity and mission of institutions focused on the promotion of cultural heritage than others. While, for example, the new copyright framework for press publishers and online platforms is certainly extremely important for the growth of the Digital Single Market, the evaluation conducted is centred on the activities and goals of CHIs, and only a few of the policy objectives can be said to be directly connected to that sector.

As such, the rationales of the DSM Directive that will be used as components of the evaluative framework to assess the impact of normative elements of the Directive in the activities of CHIs, are:

(1) To promote cultural diversity and enabling cultural preservation and dissemination practices, (2) by adapting exceptions and limitations to extend the scope of copyright rules to the digital and cross-border environment, (3) thus modernizing the sector and mitigating legal uncertainties caused by technological

These policy objectives are identified as being the ones that directly target CHIs as beneficiaries and may be helpful to promote their role in the Digital Single Market. On account of these being core

²³ Recital 2: "The directives that have been adopted in the area of copyright and related rights contribute to the functioning of the internal market, provide for a high level of protection for rightholders, facilitate the clearance of rights, and create a framework in which the exploitation of works and other protected subject matter can take place. That harmonised legal framework contributes to the proper functioning of the internal market, and stimulates innovation, creativity, investment and production of new content, also in the digital environment, in order to avoid the fragmentation of the internal market. The protection provided by that legal framework also contributes to the Union's objective of respecting and promoting cultural diversity, while at the same time bringing European common cultural heritage to the fore (...)". Recital 3: "(...) Relevant legislation needs to be future-proof so as not to restrict technological development. The objectives and the principles laid down by the Union copyright framework remain sound. However, legal uncertainty remains, for both rightholders and users, as regards certain uses, including cross-border uses, of works and other subject matter in the digital environment. (...)".

policy objectives for the Digital Single Market Strategy, each one of them is further developed both in the CDSM Directive’s Proposal’s Explanatory Memorandum, and on the Directive Recitals.

3.2.1. Promote cultural diversity

The legal basis for European intervention on the cultural sector is justified by Article 3(3) of the Treaty on European Union²⁴, setting the respect for the Union’s “rich cultural and linguistic diversity” and the protection of Europe’s cultural heritage as a priority. While, according to Article 167 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union²⁵, national diversity needs to be respected when pursuing cultural objectives, and exclusive competence on cultural policy is given to Member States, the Union is competent for the promotion, encouragement, and contribution to “the flowering of the cultures of the Member States” to bring “common cultural heritage to the fore”.

This objective of “respecting and promoting cultural diversity while at the same time bringing European common cultural heritage to the fore” is expressly mentioned on Recital 2 of the CDSM Directive as one of the rationales for the protection provided by that legal framework.

According to Section 3 (Stakeholder Consultations and Impact Assessments) of the Explanatory Memorandum of the Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of The Council on copyright in the Digital Single Market (COM/2016/0593 - 2016/0280), new copyright exceptions that reduce (to some extent) the monopolies of rightsholders are justified by other public interest objectives. These new exceptions based on public interest objectives are, therefore, “likely to have a positive impact on cultural diversity”.

The assessment of the value of a norm in promoting cultural diversity is, therefore, driven by a reflection on the potential impact of the legal text. Within the context of the evaluative matrix, this requirement will be met if the provision/norm has the potential to either: a) increase the visibility, accessibility, or dissemination of European culture, both to its citizens or to “the fore”, b) create

²⁴ Article 3(3) of the TEU: “The Union shall establish an internal market. (...) It shall respect its rich cultural and linguistic diversity, and shall ensure that Europe’s cultural heritage is safeguarded and enhanced.”

²⁵ Article 167 TFEU:

“1. The Union shall contribute to the flowering of the cultures of the Member States, while respecting their national and regional diversity and at the same time bringing the common cultural heritage to the fore.

2. Action by the Union shall be aimed at encouraging cooperation between Member States and, if necessary, supporting and supplementing their action in the following areas: improvement of the knowledge and dissemination of the culture and history of the European peoples, conservation and safeguarding of cultural heritage of European significance, non-commercial cultural exchanges, artistic and literary creation, including in the audiovisual sector.

3. The Union and the Member States shall foster cooperation with third countries and the competent international organisations in the sphere of culture, in particular the Council of Europe.

4. The Union shall take cultural aspects into account in its action under other provisions of the Treaties, in particular in order to respect and to promote the diversity of its cultures.

5. In order to contribute to the achievement of the objectives referred to in this Article: the European Parliament and the Council acting in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure and after consulting the Committee of the Regions, shall adopt incentive measures, excluding any harmonisation of the laws and regulations of the Member States, the Council, on a proposal from the Commission, shall adopt recommendations.”

better conditions for cultural creation within Europe or c) contribute to the creation or maintenance of conditions that enable future generations to retain access to cultural assets.

3.2.2. Adapting the copyright framework to the digital environment.

Another one of the goals of the CDSM Directive is to expand the copyright framework to the digital environment. The scope of prior exceptions and limitations set out in prior copyright legislation such as Directive 2001/209 (InfoSoc Directive) is formulated in view of novel technological developments of the information society (the advent of personal computers, widespread access to the internet, digital copy technology, on-demand transmission). However, such formulation is not prepared for a fully digitized cultural society, nor able to foresee the exponential increase of available computing power and the magnitude of its impact on new technological uses (data mining, neural networks, cloud computing, digital learning, 3D scanning technologies).

As Section 1 (Context) of the Explanatory Memorandum of the Proposal for the CDSM Directive puts it: “In the digital environment, cross-border uses have also intensified (...). Even though the objectives and principles laid down by the EU copyright framework remain sound, there is a need to adapt it to these new realities.”. The Explanatory Memorandum also recognizes that, although new developments in digital technologies should theoretically facilitate cross-border access to works, obstacles remain, particularly when it comes to complex cross-border rights clearance. The inability of prior copyright legislation to yield the same effects in the digital environment ultimately means “that European citizens miss opportunities to access cultural heritage.”.

Recitals 3 and 5 of the CDSM Directive confirm this ambition to conciliate the merits of the established copyright framework with the characteristics and advantages of the online setting. According to Recital 3, “the existing exceptions and limitations in Union law that are relevant for scientific research, innovation, teaching and preservation of cultural heritage should be reassessed”, and thus, Recital 5 establishes that the CDSM Directive “provides for rules to adapt certain exceptions and limitations to copyright and related rights to digital and cross-border environments.”.

The assessment of this requirement is driven by a reflection on its potential effectiveness in adapting the copyright framework to the cross-border environment. Within the context of the evaluative matrix, this requirement will be met if the provision/norm has the potential to: a) expand the scope of established copyright rules to recognize and embrace common uses in an online setting, either by b) diluting barriers in the dissemination access, and flow of cultural content between European Member-States, or c) adapting those rules to conform to the open, dematerialized, non-territorial nature of the online space, in the context of the activities of CHIs and their beneficiaries.

3.2.3. Modernizing the sector and mitigating uncertainties caused by technological progress.

The third policy goal of the CDSM Directive used as a requirement in the evaluative matrix is the “modernisation of certain aspects of the Union copyright framework to take account of

technological developments and new channels of distribution of protected content in the internal market”²⁶. Once again, Recital 3 of the Directive describes this objective quite clearly:

“Rapid technological developments continue to transform the way works and other subject-matter are created, produced, distributed, and exploited. New business models and new actors continue to emerge. The objectives and the principles laid down by the Union copyright framework remain sound. However, legal uncertainty remains, for both rightholders and users, as regards certain uses, including cross-border uses, of works and other subject-matter in the digital environment.”

As is the case with any set of policy objectives that define the direction and goals of a legal instrument, all the policy objectives of the CDSM Directive are undoubtedly interlinked in several ways. The evaluative matrix’s requirement number 2 (adaptation of the copyright framework to extend its scope to the digital and cross-border environment) is driven by the general interests of promoting cultural diversity (requirement 1) and a well-functioning internal marketplace and can ultimately result in the modernization of all the target sectors, and the suppression of legal uncertainties caused by the dissonance between new available technologies and the copyright status quo.

According to Section 1 (Context) of the Explanatory Memorandum of the Proposal for a Directive on Copyright in The Digital Single Market, this modernized framework would benefit all sectoral actors with the legal space to use all kinds of innovative tools and technologies with no uncertainties.

The assessment of this requirement is therefore driven by a reflection on its potential of wielding success in mitigating legal uncertainty associated to new technologies and activities. Within the context of the evaluative matrix, this requirement will be met if the provision/norm has the potential to: a) regulate a new technology or a new use of a technology and b) mitigate or entirely suppress any legal uncertainty associated with that particular technology or use while c) keeping and respecting the objectives of the copyright framework and the Union’s principles.

3.3. Open culture and the promotion of cultural reuse

The three requirements insofar outlined and described have been selected for being the most appropriate to provide for a theoretical assessment of the potential that the CDSM Directive has to create a space for CHIs to conduct their activity more freely and effectively. These are centred on

²⁶ Former Recital 44 of the CDSM Directive, according to the Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on copyright in the Digital Single Market COM/2016/0593: “The objectives of this Directive, namely the modernisation of certain aspects of the Union copyright framework to take account of technological developments and new channels of distribution of protected content in the internal market, cannot be sufficiently achieved by Member States but can rather, by reason of their scale, effects and cross-border dimension, be better achieved at Union level. Therefore, the Union may adopt measures in accordance with the principle of subsidiarity as set out in Article 5 of the Treaty on European Union. In accordance with the principle of proportionality, as set out in that Article, this Directive does not go beyond what is necessary in order to achieve those objectives.”

proliferating creation of and access to culture through new rules made for the digital environment that suppress the uncertainties associated to it.

In 2011, before the introduction of the Strategy for a Digital Single Market, the European Commission identified, in its 2011 Recommendation on the digitisation and online accessibility of cultural material and digital preservation (Recommendation 2011/711/EU, of 27 October 2011), the need to provide an updated set of measures for digitising and bringing cultural heritage online. According to Recital 6 of the Recommendation, the digitisation of cultural assets will “help Europe’s cultural institutions to continue carrying out their mission of giving access to and preserving our heritage in the digital environment.”, and that this material shall be subject to reuse, for both commercial and non-commercial purposes, “provided that this is done with full respect for copyright and related rights.”.

It is, therefore, evident that the Commission recognises the relevance of creating a framework for cultural reuse that does not directly collide or conflict with the exploitation of exclusive rights over works. Accordingly, “only part of the material held by libraries, archives and museums is in the public domain, in the sense that it is not or is no longer covered by intellectual property rights, while the rest is protected by intellectual property rights. Since intellectual property rights are a key tool to stimulate creativity, Europe’s cultural material should be digitised, made available and preserved in full respect of copyright and related rights.”²⁷.

More recently, the Recommendation was subject to review leading to the publication of 2021 Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970 of 10 November 2021 on a common European data space for cultural heritage, declaring that “several of the challenges faced by the cultural heritage sector 10 years ago are still present today”.

The 2021 Recommendation recognizes the merits of the CDSM Directive in “modernising the copyright framework that governs how cultural heritage institutions operate in the digital environment”²⁸ and “encourages Member States to put in place appropriate frameworks to enhance the recovery and transformation of the cultural heritage sector and to support cultural heritage institutions in becoming more empowered and more resilient in the future.”²⁹. Such a transformation would lead to higher quality digitization and reuse across the European Union. Although the promotion of cultural reuse is not explicitly mentioned as a goal of the CDSM Directive, it is undoubtedly a core goal of the digital transformation of the cultural sector as envisioned by the European Union³⁰.

²⁷ Recital 11 of the COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION of 27 October 2011 on the digitisation and online accessibility of cultural material and digital preservation (2011/711/EU).

²⁸ Recital 16 of COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2021/1970 of 10 November 2021 on a common European data space for cultural heritage.

²⁹ Recital 6 of COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2021/1970 of 10 November 2021 on a common European data space for cultural heritage.

³⁰ Recital 6 of COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2021/1970 of 10 November 2021 on a common European data space for cultural heritage: “This Recommendation encourages Member States to put in place appropriate frameworks to enhance the recovery and transformation of the cultural heritage sector and to support cultural heritage institutions in becoming more empowered and more resilient in the future. This will lead to higher quality digitisation, reuse and digital preservation across the EU, and have spillover effects in

Taking into consideration that copyright law has always been at the centre of the debate on cultural reuse³¹ and that the overarching goal of the inDICEs project is to empower the Cultural and Creative Industries and policymakers to fully understand the social and economic impact of digitization and the innovative reuse of cultural assets, the potential to enable creative reuse needs to be included as a criterion for the assessment of the impact of copyright regulation on the cultural sector.

While the three previously delineated requirements are used to assess the compliance of the Directive with its self-determined goals, the potential for creative reuse is an overarching metric for the empowerment of the cultural sector³² that is not necessarily present even if the objectives of promoting cultural diversity, modernising copyright, and suppressing legal uncertainties are strictly pursued. In fact, it might very well be that a provision of the CDSM Directive complies with those goals, thus benefiting cultural heritage institutions and the public in their activities, but concomitantly does not go beyond those goals by enabling cultural reuse. An example of such a situation would be the framework of Article 8 of the CDSM Directive, on the use of out-of-commerce works and other subject matter by cultural heritage institutions³³.

As is explained in a later chapter, Article 8 promotes the access to cultural heritage by allowing institutions to reproduce, distribute and provide (online) access to in-copyright works in their collections that are not available in customary channels of commerce. However, its scope is limited to a subset of uses (only cultural heritage establishments can perform those actions, and those actions only), even if the provision promotes cultural diversity and updates the array of available exceptions and limitations to compute with cross-border uses. Any further uses downstream (like reuse and adaptation) are not made permissible by the provision.

Therefore, in line with the objectives of the inDICEs project and in recognition of the value of the promotion of cultural reuse in the European Union's approach to the modernization of the cultural section, this element is included in the evaluative matrix. Within the context of the evaluative matrix, this requirement will be met if the provision/norm has the potential to: a) enable the digital availability of cultural goods to the public, b) through efforts of mass digitisation or by disseminating collections, c) so that these cultural assets can be subject to reuse, either commercially or non-commercially, by members of the public.

3.4. Assessing (im)balance in a CHI-centred evaluation.

The analysis insofar developed allows us to recognise that the European's Union stark dedication to valuing and promoting public interests has always been contraposed to the need to keep a balance

other key sectors of the European economy, such as tourism, research, and other cultural and creative sectors.”.

³¹ Andrea Wallace & Ellen Euler, *Revisiting Access to Cultural Heritage in the Public Domain: EU and International Developments* (2020), IIC 51, 823–855, <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40319-020-00961-8>> accessed 14 November 2022.

³² Aleksandra Janus, Alek Tarkowski, Jan Strycharz & Maria Drabczyk, *Deliverable 3.1: Policy analysis of value chains for CHIs in the Digital Single Market* (2021), <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5140001>> accessed 14 November 2022.

³³ See section 5.1. of the present document.

with other interests, be them parallel public policy objectives, or the protection of the fundamental rights of authors³⁴. According to the Union's principles, only that way can it conserve the stability and promote the growth of the internal market. Generally speaking, since cultural interests are a public policy objective, the favouring of these will always happen in detriment of, or rather, in compromise with the protection of individual exclusive rights.

When assessing the potential that a rule or set of rules have to benefit a particular stakeholder, that benefit is indissociable with the symmetrical detriment to another stakeholder, and vice-versa. It is not only relevant to assess how objectively beneficial (or not) a rule might be for the flourishing of the cultural sector, but also important to engage in subjective consideration on its relationship with the other interests at stake.

Considering that this is an assessment centred on the impact of copyright regulation on the activities of cultural heritage institutions, the evaluation of their paper in the Digital Single Market and of the recognition and valuation of that role in the modernization of the copyright acquis cannot be done from an isolated standpoint, but in a way that illustrates what concessions the policymaker was willing to make in favour of the cultural sector.

While, ideally, a provision would be deemed better the more beneficial to the cultural sector it appeared to be, such a perspective is not compatible with the need to keep a balanced internal market and level playing field for all parties involved. As such, the fifth and final element of the evaluative matrix sets out to provide an assessment of which stakeholders have been prioritized in the provision under scrutiny, and how the European legislator established (or not) a compromise with parallel or colliding interests.

³⁴ Article 27(2) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: "Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author."

Figure 1 - Graphic representation of the Evaluative Framework

3.5. Applying the evaluative matrix

As previously asserted, the DSM Directive is divided into five titles: Title I containing General Provisions (subject matter, scope, definitions); Title II, laying out measures to adapt exceptions and limitations to the digital environment (Data mining, education, cultural preservation); Title III, on licensing practices (out-of-commerce works, collective licensing, protection of the public domain); Title IV on measures to achieve a well-functioning marketplace for copyright (press publisher's rights, online content-sharing service providers and fair remuneration of authors and performers) and Title V, containing final provisions. For structural cohesion purposes, the upcoming chapters of the present document adhere to the same structural system as the one found in the Directive.

In each of the ensuing chapters, the relevant provisions of that chapter are highlighted according to their (positive or negative) relevance to the activity of CHIs in the Digital Single Market, thus determining the application of the matrix – only in the case that a provision does not affect the activities of CHIs, either because these are not foreseen as beneficiaries or because the sphere of action of the beneficiary is so distant that it does not produce any effects on the activities of cultural institutions, shall the matrix not apply.

In any other case, a sub-chapter will be individually dedicated to each of the highlighted Articles. Because the legislative technique deployed by the European legislator makes it so that the normative elements contained in a single provision can be manifold, the general application of the evaluative matrix to an Article of the Directive requires prior identification and description of the distinct elements that influence this assessment. Each sub-chapter, dedicated to an Article of the DSM Directive, is introduced by a breakdown of the distinct elements that facilitate an objective analysis of each article, and that may influence the application of the evaluative framework to the provision in general, which is performed at the end of the sub-chapter. Although each of these

elements affects the final assessment the Article under study, applying the evaluative matrix to every individual element would not yield productive results, as the scope of each of these is fairly limited and their merits or pitfalls are taken into consideration collectively in the assessment of the Article.

The structure for all the subsequent chapters is as follows: a chapter, correspondent to a Title of the Directive is introduced with a highlight of relevant Articles contained within. Each of the sub-chapters, dedicated to individual Articles, are introduced by a summary of the context. The breakdown and description of the normative elements contained in the provision is performed by dedicating an individual sub-section to each element. Then, the last sub-section of the sub-chapter is dedicated to applying the evaluative matrix (5 criteria and a general assessment) to the Article under scrutiny in that sub-chapter. This exercise culminates with an overarching chapter conclusion which summarizes the results of the evaluative assessment. This summary is accompanied by a graphic representation in form of a table similar to the one found below, highlighting the normative elements and the influence they had in the application of the evaluative matrix to the Articles.

Chapter § – Title #						
	Fostering Cultural Diversity	Adaptation to the digital environment	Suppression of technological uncertainties	Enabling creative reuse	Fair balance of interests	General evaluation of the Article (CHI – centred)
Sub-Chapter §.1 – Provision (Article X)						
§.1.1 - Element X-1	+	+	-	-	+	
§.1.2 - Element X-2	+	+	-	-	-	
§.1.3 - Element X-3	+	0	0	+	+	
§.1.4 - Element X-4	+	0	0	-	-	
Assessment of Article X:	+	+	0	-	0	
Sub-Chapter §.Y – Article Y (Title of the provision)						
§.Y.1 - Element Y-1						
§.Y.2 - Element Y-2						
S.Y.3 - Element Y-3						
(...)						

Table 1 – Sample of a simplified final chapter summary.

Note: *Green* means “Positive”; *Orange* means “Neutral” or “N/A”; *Red* means “Negative”. “. Overall assessment (darker shading) is performed based on the average classification of selected elements. In case of a tie or 1-point difference, priority is given to a positive assessment to avoid negative bias. Subtitles (+, 0, -) added for accessibility purposes.

4 Title II – Exceptions and limitations (Articles 3 to 7)

Title II of the CDSM Directive (Measures to adapt exceptions and limitations to the cross-border environment) is dedicated to updating the copyright framework for the fields of research, innovation, education, and preservation of cultural heritage³⁵. According to Recital 5 of the Directive, “Mandatory exceptions or limitations for uses of text and data mining technologies, illustration for teaching in the digital environment and for preservation of cultural heritage should be introduced”.

Following these objectives, Title II comprises a total of 6 Articles. Articles 3 and 4 of the CDSM Directive introduce two new mandatory exceptions for reproductions and extractions for the purposes of text and data mining. The core difference between the two Articles, and the reason for their separation lies on the purposes for which the processes of text and data mining are carried out. On the one hand, processing done by specific types of non-profit organisations for purposes of scientific research is given particular treatment in Article 3. Conversely, all remaining purposes and entities, including commercial activities and establishments, fit within the scope of Article 4³⁶.

Article 5 of the CDSM Directive is dedicated to the institution of a new (mandatory) exception for the use of works and other subject matter in digital and cross-border teaching activities. It introduces rules on the types of educational materials that can be disseminated online, on the security of digital learning environments, and on the fair compensation for rightsholders whose works are used in this context³⁷.

The penultimate provision, Article 6, establishes a set of rules for the lawful reproduction of works for the purposes of cultural preservation. Finally, Article 7 of the CDSM Directive, titled “Common provisions” introduces a contractual override and a technological override safeguard for the application of the exceptions included in Title II³⁸.

³⁵ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021)

³⁶ Thomas Margoni, Martin Kretschmer, *A Deeper Look into the EU Text and Data Mining Exceptions: Harmonisation, Data Ownership, and the Future of Technology* (2022), *GRUR International* 71(8) 685–701, <<<https://doi.org/10.1093/grurint/ikac054>>> accessed 15 November 2022.

³⁷ João Pedro Quintais, *The New Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive: A Critical Look* (2020), *European Intellectual Property Review* 42(1), 28-41, <<<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3424770>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

³⁸ The European Copyright Society, *Comment of the European Copyright Society Addressing Selected Aspects of the Implementation of Articles 3 to 7 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 on Copyright in the Digital Single Market* (2020), <<https://europeancopyrightsociety.org/2022/05/03/https-europeancopyrightsocietydotorg-files-wordpress-com-2022-05-ecs_exceptions_final-1-pdf/>> accessed 14 November 2022.

4.1. – Text and data mining for research purposes (Article 3)

Introduction and Context

Article 3 of the CDSM Directive requires Member States to introduce a mandatory exception to copyright, related rights, and database rights for the purposes of mass data analytics³⁹. The beneficiaries foreseen in the text of Article 3 are research organisations and cultural heritage organisations that wish to perform data mining of copyrighted works. According to the provision, these institutions can carry out such operations on works or other subject matter they have lawful access to and retain copies of those assets as long as secure storage obligations are met⁴⁰. Such obligations can be complemented by measures to ensure the security and integrity of hosting networks and databases by rightsholders.

4.1.1. Element 1: Beneficiaries and scientific research purpose

Some context on the motivation for the introduction of this Article is found in Recitals 8 to 17. Accordingly, text and data mining make the processing of large amounts of information with a view to gaining new knowledge and discovering new trends possible, which can be of great advantage to universities, research organizations and cultural heritage institutions. As such, the mandatory exception to the exclusive right of reproduction and to the right to prevent extraction from a database is justified by its scientific research purposes⁴¹. The term “scientific research” should be understood as embracing both natural and human sciences. Institutionally, and despite “different legal forms and structures, (...) research organizations in the Member States generally have in common that they act either on a not-for-profit basis or in the context of a public-interest mission”⁴². It is, therefore, evident that the beneficiaries of the exception cannot be institutions directed and prioritizing the generation of revenue or dividends, and must exist either on a not-for-profit basis, or pursue objectives of public interest⁴³.

Article 3(1) of the DSM Directive explicitly makes mention to “research organizations and cultural heritage institutions”. The latter are defined as covering “publicly accessible libraries and museums, regardless of the type of works or other subject matter that they hold in their permanent collections, as well as archives, film or audio heritage institutions”, as well as national libraries and

³⁹ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021)

⁴⁰ Thomas Margoni, Martin Kretschmer, *A Deeper Look into the EU Text and Data Mining Exceptions: Harmonisation, Data Ownership, and the Future of Technology* (2022), *GRUR International* 71(8) 685–701, <<<https://doi.org/10.1093/grurint/ikac054>>> accessed 15 November 2022.

⁴¹ Giulia Dore, Marta Arisi & Roberto Caso, *D5.1 Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) in EU* (2021). <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5070449>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁴² Bernt Hugenholtz, *The New Copyright Directive: Text and Data Mining (Articles 3 and 4)* (2019), *Kluwer Copyright Blog*, <<<http://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2019/07/24/the-new-copyright-directive-text-and-data-mining-articles-3-and-4/>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁴³ COMMUNIA, *DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines*, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

archives and, “as far as their archives and publicly accessible libraries are concerned, educational establishments, research organisations and public sector organisations”.

Therefore, and according to Recital 12, the beneficiaries of Article 3 of the DSM Directive can be defined as being any institution “the primary goal of which is to conduct scientific research or to do so together with the provision of educational services”, as well as any cultural heritage institution⁴⁴.

Adding to this widely delineated set of beneficiaries, Recital 14 further complements this definition by stating that “research organisations and cultural heritage institutions, including the persons attached thereto, should be covered by the text and data mining exception with regard to content to which they have lawful access.”. While this may seem evident, since a legal entity does not have the ability to perform a human task of scientific research, the clarification is much welcome, as it suppresses any leverage for argumentation against the application of the exception based on the role or affiliation of the scientist conducting the text and data mining operation. Scientist are entitled to perform all of the operations foreseen by the exception, as long as they are affiliated to one of the beneficiaries, and make a scientific use⁴⁵.

The same logic also applies in the case of a public-private partnership. In fact, as will be the case with many of the new exceptions, which are directly catered to regulating novel technological developments and the necessary consequent uses of that technology, some institutions may be interested in performing text and data mining operations but not be in possession of the technology necessary to do so. As such, and according to Recital 11, “while research organisations and cultural heritage institutions should continue to be the beneficiaries of that exception, they should also be able to rely on their private partners for carrying out text and data mining, including by using their technological tools.”. In conclusion, it is possible for a research organization or cultural heritage institution to outsource the data mining tasks that they want to perform on their collections⁴⁶.

4.1.2. Element 2: Scope of the exception

The exception allows its beneficiaries to perform reproductions and operates as an exemption from Article 5(a) (exclusive right to carry out or to authorize temporary or permanent reproduction by any means and in any form, in whole or in part of a database which is protectable by copyright) and 7(1) (right for the maker of a sui generis database to prevent extraction and/or re-utilization of the whole or of a substantial part of the contents of that database) of Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases, as well as

⁴⁴ LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries), Europe’s TDM Exception for Research: Will It Be Undermined By Technical Blocking From Publishers? (2020), <<<https://libereurope.eu/article/tdm-technical-protection-measures/>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁴⁵ The European Copyright Society, Comment of the European Copyright Society Addressing Selected Aspects of the Implementation of Articles 3 to 7 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 on Copyright in the Digital Single Market (2020), <<https://europeancopyrightsociety.org/2022/05/03/https-europeancopyrightsocietydotorg-files-wordpress-com-2022-05-ecs_exceptions_final-1-pdf/>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁴⁶ Thomas Margoni, Martin Kretschmer, A Deeper Look into the EU Text and Data Mining Exceptions: Harmonisation, Data Ownership, and the Future of Technology (2022), GRUR International 71(8) 685–701, <<<https://doi.org/10.1093/grurint/ikac054>>> accessed 15 November 2022.

Article 2 of the InfoSoc Directive (reproductions of works and other protected subject matter)⁴⁷ and Article 15 of the DSM Directive (reproduction of press publications)

The scope of the exception is, therefore, limited to acts of reproduction of copyrighted works and databases, other protected subject matter, such as subject matter protected by neighbouring rights (recordings, performances, broadcasts, publications), sui generis databases and press publications. As such, the text of Article 3(1) of the DSM Directive appears to have left out computer programs, as defined and protected by Directive 2009/24/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the legal protection of computer programs from the scope of the exception. This is not an accidental exclusion, as the scope of Article 4 explicitly mentions the Software Directive when defining its scope⁴⁸.

Furthermore, these acts can be commercial in nature, as long as the institution is not a for-profit organization⁴⁹. Article 3(1) clearly does not exclude the possibility for the text and data mining operations to have commercial viability, an interpretation that is validated by Recital 11 of the DSM Directive, which states that, in order to boost the Union’s research efforts and development of a reliable technological framework, universities and research institutes are encouraged “to collaborate with the private sector” and that “research organisations should also benefit from such an exception when their research activities are carried out in the framework of public-private partnerships.”. As was mentioned in the previous section, it is possible for a research organization or cultural heritage institution to outsource the data science tasks that they want to perform on their collections, and, in that case, those partners would still be covered by the exception, even if they are for-profit organizations.

Finally, it is well established that the application exception in Article 3 of the DSM Directive does not entitle the rightsholder to any sort of remuneration. According to Recital 17 of the Directive, “any potential harm created to rightholders through this exception would be minimal” and “Member States should, therefore, not provide for compensation for rightholders as regards uses under the text and data mining exceptions introduced by this Directive.”⁵⁰.

4.1.3. Element 3: Lawful access

The concept of “lawful access” is crucial for the application of the exception provided for in Article 3 of the DSM Directive. Recital 14 clarifies the notion of lawful access in regard to text and data mining performed for scientific research purposes by defining it as “covering access to content based on an open access policy or through contractual arrangements between rightsholders and research

⁴⁷ Marie-Christine Janssens, Arina Gorbatyuk, & Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, Deliverable 2.1: Mapping of the relevant European IP legal framework (2021), <<<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141439>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁴⁸ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁴⁹ Giulia Dore, Marta Arisi & Roberto Caso, D5.1 Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) in EU (2021). <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5070449>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁵⁰ Christophe Geiger & Giancarlo Frosio & Oleksandr Bulayenko, Text and Data Mining: Articles 3 and 4 of the Directive 2019/790/EU (2019), <<[10.2139/ssrn.3470653](https://ssrn.com/abstract=3470653)>> accessed 14 November 2022.

organisations or cultural heritage institutions, such as subscriptions”, as well as “content that is freely available online”. The deployment of the non-enumerative terminology, particularly the terms “such as” and “for instance”, imply that the examples provided are non-exhaustive and that the concept of “lawful access” is, therefore, an open-ended one. The particular modalities of access depicted in the Recital serve as example, but any form of access that is granted freely, through consent or contract, or other means, provided that these means do not unlawfully surpass technical barriers or make works available without the knowledge or consent of the rightsholder, shall be deemed lawful and valid for the purpose of the application of Article 3⁵¹. All in all, this would hypothetically mean that if the institutions have a right to use the content, either because they acquired/licensed or because it is freely available on the open web, they have a right to perform text and data mining operations. The truth is not so linear, as is explained in Sub-section 4.1.5.

4.1.4. Element 4: Secure storage obligations and network integrity measures

According to Article 3(2) the beneficiaries of Article 3 have to comply with the obligation to securely store copies of works or other protected subject matter that they have made for the purposes of text and data mining. If the appropriate secure storage obligations are followed⁵², copies “may be retained for the purpose of scientific research, including for the verification of research results”. This level of security is not defined in the Directive and, as Recital 15 clarifies, such task is left to Member States, which “should be free to decide, at a national level and after discussions with relevant stakeholders, on further specific arrangements for retaining copies”. Recital 15 also highlights that, regardless of the nature and scope of the arrangements for securely retaining copies, the threshold of secure storage is met when unauthorised use is considered to be prevented. This “unauthorised use” covers any other use that does not equate to a text and data mining operation, except for derivative scientific uses, such as peer review of scientific results, and efforts of joint research, which are covered by Article 5(3)(a) of the InfoSoc Directive⁵³. The Directive sets no time limit on the storage of this data, which technically mean it could be kept forever as long as security obligations are consistently met. This will, of course, always depend on the data management policy of the particular institutions, but the Directive imposes no time limits.

The secure storage obligation, albeit based on a legitimate concern, raises some issues: cultural heritage institutions, universities and research organisations already spend significant effort and capital in storage solutions to ensure adequate security of their content, which makes it redundant to prescribe an external secure storage obligation to these institutions⁵⁴. Similarly, data scientists are highly trained professionals that are aware of the specific storage needs for the data being used in a particular context. As the LIBER organization puts it, reflecting on this inappropriateness to prescribe

⁵¹ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021)

⁵² Giulia Dore, Marta Arisi & Roberto Caso, *D5.1 Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) in EU* (2021). <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5070449>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁵³ Marie-Christine Janssens, Arina Gorbayuk, & Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, *Deliverable 2.1: Mapping of the relevant European IP legal framework* (2021), <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141439>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁵⁴ COMMUNIA, *DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines*, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

storage obligations to highly technical institutions and professionals, “Trusted to Buy – Trusted to Use”⁵⁵.

4.1.5. Element 5: Network integrity measures

In order to mitigate the risk of unauthorised access, these storage obligations can be complemented with network security measures implemented by the rightsholders. According to Article 3(3) of the DSM Directive, rightsholders “shall be allowed to apply measures to ensure the security and integrity of the networks and databases where the works or other subject matter are hosted. Such measures shall not go beyond what is necessary to achieve that objective.”

This means that rightsholders can ultimately attempt to protect their content by implementing technical protection measures that allow the text and data mining operations, while keeping it secure from unintended use. However, it is not clear how this may be implemented in a way that ensures the full enjoyment of the exception – while beneficiaries of the exception can certainly lodge complaints and requests to Member States to allow access to particular works that are restricted by disproportional technical measures, these access request systems are generally known to be inefficient and bureaucratic⁵⁶.

Normal access control measures such as challenge–response reverse Turing tests (a common example of which is a captcha test, which asks the human accessing the website or content to insert the characters visible in a pictorial prompt)⁵⁷ are commonly put in place to avoid bots and other fraudulent automated programs to sign up to and enter websites or access content. While this generally a valid strategy to ensure that a human is on the other side of the screen, when dealing with automated data processing tasks, such a trivial and usual human verification test can stonewall legitimate and lawful text and data mining operations.

Another example of a common cybersecurity measure that can frustrate text and data mining operations is rate-limiting access-control filters, put in place as a protection measure against denial-of-service attacks, a cyber-attack in which the perpetrator floods a service network with access requests in an attempt to disrupt the network and make it unresponsive or unavailable (crash)⁵⁸. Once again, and while rate-limiting access-control measures serve a legitimate purpose, an automated content scraper, being legitimately used for a text and data mining operation, can trigger the access-control filters by requesting access to multiple network resources in a short period of

⁵⁵ LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries), *The Right to Read is the Right To Mine: But Not When Blocked by Technical Protection Measures* (2019), <<<https://libereurope.eu/article/the-right-to-read-is-the-right-to-mine-but-not-when-blocked-by-technical-protection-measures/>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁵⁶ COMMUNIA, *DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines*, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁵⁷ Fatemeh Alizadeh, Aikaterini Mniestri & Gunnar Stevens, *The Reverse Turing Test: Being Human (is) enough in the Age of AI* (2022), *Proceedings of CoPDA2022 - Sixth International Workshop on Cultures of Participation in the Digital Age: AI for Humans or Humans for AI?*, <<https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3136/paper-7.pdf>>, accessed 15 November 2022.

⁵⁸ Uwe Aickelin & Gianni Tedesco, *Data Reduction in Intrusion Alert Correlation* (2006), <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2824155>> accessed 15 November 2022.

time. In this case, the content would become unavailable to the beneficiaries' internet protocol address, and frustrate any attempts at legitimately accessing, downloading, and using content in the context of the exception⁵⁹.

While the matter of circumvention of technical protection measures is dealt with in Article 7, it is important to assert that, particularly in the case of text and data mining, which commonly makes use of automated content access methods, expedited solutions to remove measures that frustrate this use are crucial.

Application of the Evaluative Matrix to Article 3 of the DSM Directive:

i) Cultural diversity:

Although it includes cultural heritage institutions as beneficiaries, the text and data mining exception seems to contemplate the role of their collections from a scientific potential perspective, and not from their cultural value. The exception does not increase the visibility of European culture, since research materials need to be kept in secure storage and are only visible to the scientists performing the authorized operations on them. Furthermore, even if it could be argued that the production of high-quality scientific research that included cultural material in the form of research output would be responsible for increasing the visibility of European culture, the reality is that the exception does not contemplate the public sharing of research output that includes the copyrighted materials. The scope of the exception for text and data mining for scientific purposes is clearly defined as only affecting the right of reproduction, and the sharing of copyrighted works with a public not initially prescribed or authorized by the rightsholder would fall under the scope of the right of communication to the public.

Alternatively, it can be argued that this exception serves as a driver for cultural heritage institutions to seek private collaborations, build capacity regarding digitisation practices, and even acquire or temporarily obtain access to digitisation technology. The exception does break, to a certain extent, the monopolistic nature of copyright, allowing CHIs to diversify the information mined, and the enlarged and fairly unrestricted scope of the exception might be complimentary to other digitisation activities targeted at promoting cultural diversity.

ii) Adaptation to the cross-border environment:

Overall, Article 3 completely ignores the objective of adapting the copyright acquis to the open, dematerialized, non-territorial nature of the online space, and focuses only on the objective to drive technological progress forwards. This perspective is based on the fact that any digital use entails a communication to the public, and this exception does not affect that exclusive right, as has been previously pointed out.

Therefore, the establishment of a partnership with another organisation (or multiple organisations) located in another Member State would require the constant back-and-forth transportation of

⁵⁹ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

research materials and research data in analogue form, which is the exact opposite of a digital cross-border environment.

Furthermore, the lack of standard circumvention or redress mechanisms against abusive technological protection measures means that an institution collaborating with other institutions in different Member States would have to deal with severely heterogeneous approaches to access requests regarding technical protection measures.

iii) Legal certainty regarding technological developments:

Article 3 can be perceived as highly beneficial to legal certainty regarding the use of massive statistical analysis technology. The additional clarification that not only the institutions (which exist as legal persons by virtue of a legal fiction and are therefore unable to perform these operations themselves) but also the persons attached to them, as well as any partners that these institutions opt to rely on to perform this task are covered by the exception is a great step towards avoiding conflicts based on the lack of clarity. Likewise, a broad but well-delineated definition of “scientific research purposes” ascertains that the beneficiaries that could make use of the exception know they may.

However, a certain degree of uncertainty subsists regarding the aforementioned issues: the fact that the exception applies only to the exclusive right of reproduction means that there is no clear framework for cross-border collaboration, digital collaboration, and also for the sharing and publication of research data – all of which require an act of communication to the public.

While it is great to attain legal certainty in regard to the act of text and data mining itself, the technological and scientific industry is not circumscribed to the performance of those operations alone and calls for greater regulation on the matters of digital collaborative networks and the publication of research data, including research output.

iv) Cultural creative reuse:

While this exception certainly enables scientific reuse of cultural content by allowing beneficiaries to keep stored data for future scientific research prospects, that data, at least in its original form, is not being reused for any creative purposes. The exception on text and data mining for scientific research purposes does not foster the availability of cultural goods to the public nor does it promote the creative reuse of cultural assets in any way.

Ultimately, the copyrighted works utilized for text and data mining operations are subject to high standards of storage security and are only allowed to be used under this particular and well-defined pretext. Any other use of materials, even their eventual integration into research output would require authorization from the rightsholder, or the reliance on another unharmonized exception, such as the quotation exception.

Even if the materials were in the public domain, which would mean data scientists would not be working under the exception, but freely on publicly available material, their integration in research output would still not classify as cultural reuse, as this is done uniquely for scientific purposes.

v) Balance of rights:

The evaluation performed by the legislature upon creating new rules that introduce exceptions to what would otherwise be a standard of the highest level of protection for authors, rightsholders and their intellectual property, is always driven by the primacy of keeping a fair balance between the various interests at stake. Exceptions should be taken advantage of fully, and, within the framework of such an unhindered use, the moral and economic integrity of a work or protected subject matter should remain as untouched as possible.

From a balancing perspective, the recognition that the application of an exception (in this particular case, the text and data mining exception) poses no threat to the intellectual property of a rightsholder is a great primer that would optimally apply to all exceptions and limitations (which unfortunately is not the case). A broad definition of “scientific” research, the opportunity to engage in private partnerships and the absence of an obligation to provide compensation for the use of the work, are all excellent signposts of a true balancing effort that broadens the limits of the application of the exception by conceptualizing the needs of the beneficiary as non-conflicting with the interests of the rightsholder.

However, the issues concerning the (lack of) trust placed on the institutions entitled to perform highly technical scientific operations, and the lack of guidance on potential circumvention or redress mechanisms to impede or punish the deliberate obstruction to lawful access for the uses prescribed by the exception, can be seen as detrimental to the role of the beneficiaries. The overall assessment of the balance of rights is that it respects the public mission of cultural heritage institutions, and puts great value in the scientific utilization of cultural assets, albeit under a somewhat conceited prerogative of bolstering the international perspective of the role of Europe in science and technology.

4.1.B – Text and data mining for other purposes (Article 4)

Article 4 is the second provision on text and data mining introduced in the DSM Directive. It stems from a recognition of the value of text and data mining for purposes other than scientific research – Recital 18 provides some examples such as “government services, complex business decisions and the development of new applications or technologies”.

Unlike its predecessor, the exception contained in Article 4 does not have a closed list of beneficiaries or purposes. Paragraph 1 introduce an exception to reproduction rights for “reproductions and extractions of lawfully accessible works and other subject matter for the purposes of text and data mining.”. Similarly to the exception for cultural heritage institutions, lawful access to the work, as expressed in the previous section, is mandatory. Paragraph 2 allows the reproductions to be retained for as long as necessary for the purposes of text and data mining⁶⁰.

⁶⁰ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021)

Finally, Paragraph 3 establishes that this exception only applies when such uses have not been expressly excluded by the rightsholder in “an appropriate manner, such as machine-readable means in the case of content made publicly available online”. As is detailed in the section about Article 7, all the mandatory exceptions of Title II of the DSM Directive are protected against contractual override except for Article 4 – as such, if an author or rightsholder reserves their rights by specifically excluding text and data mining (except for scientific purposes), either by contract or machine-readable means (such as metadata or machine-readable webpage information such as a robots.txt exclusion protocol to communicate with web crawlers and other web robots), then the exception is not applicable and the acts are not authorized even if the user has lawful access to the work or other subject matter⁶¹.

Therefore, and due to the fact that all text and data mining activities conducted, promoted or arranged by cultural heritage institutions without license or authorization from the rightsholder will inevitably fall under the exception in Article 3, the secondary provision for text and data mining for other purposes will not be further scrutinized nor subjected to the evaluative framework as it will rarely affect the daily activities of CHIs – and in the situations it does, the application framework is similar to Article 3, except the list of beneficiaries and purposes is open, and the exception can be contractually blocked.

⁶¹ Thomas Margoni, Martin Kretschmer, A Deeper Look into the EU Text and Data Mining Exceptions: Harmonisation, Data Ownership, and the Future of Technology (2022), GRUR International 71(8) 685–701, <<<https://doi.org/10.1093/grurint/ikac054>>> accessed 15 November 2022.

4.2. – Digital and cross-border teaching activities (Article 5)

Introduction and Context

Article 5 of the DSM Directive was introduced to suppress the uncertainties associated with the application of the exception foreseen in Article 5(3)(a) of the InfoSoc Directive and Articles 6(2)(b) and 9(b) of the Database Directive⁶², which respectively allow for the reproduction and communication to the public of copyrighted works, copyrighted databases and the extraction and reuse of sui generis databases, as long as those actions are performed for the purpose of illustration for teaching. According to Recital 19 of the DSM Directive, the scope of those three exceptions when applied to the digital environment, particularly in the context of online education, is unclear, which could “hamper the development of digitally supported teaching activities and distance learning”.

Therefore, Article 5, titled “Use of works and other subject matter in digital and cross-border teaching activities” creates an exception to the aforementioned exclusive rights⁶³ to allow the digital use of works and other protected subject matter for “the sole purpose of illustration for teaching, to the extent justified by the non-commercial purpose to be achieved”.

The lawful and valid application of Article 5 is dependent on two conditions: the use needs to happen in the premises of an educational establishment, or in a secure electronic environment controlled by such an establishment, and, unless impossible, the material is accompanied by an indication of the source, including the author’s name⁶⁴.

Although the implementation of the core provisions of Article 5 is mandatory, some optional choices are given to Member-States, namely, the possibility to: only allow for specific portions or percentages of a specific type of work to be used, establish a priority in licensing over the application of the exception for specific types of work, and to demand fair compensation for rightsholders when this exception is used⁶⁵.

4.2.1. Element 1: Scope and beneficiaries (formal educators)

According to Recital 22, the exception for the purpose of illustration for teaching in Article 5 should only “take place in the context of teaching and learning activities carried out under the responsibility

⁶² Marie-Christine Janssens, Arina Gorbatyuk, & Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, Deliverable 2.1: Mapping of the relevant European IP legal framework (2021), <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141439>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁶³ Reproduction and communication of a work and other protected subject matter, reproduction, adaptation and communication to the public of a copyrighted database, extraction and reuse of a sui generis database and reproduction, adaptation and distribution of computer programs, reproduction and communication to the public of press publications.

⁶⁴ Giulia Dore, Marta Arisi & Roberto Caso, D5.1 Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) in EU (2021). <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5070449>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁶⁵ Bernd Justin Jütte, The New Copyright Directive: Digital and Cross-border Teaching Exception (Article 5) (2019), Kluwer Copyright Blog, <<<http://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2019/06/21/the-new-copyright-directive-digital-and-cross-border-teaching-exception-article-5/>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

of educational establishments”. The concept of “educational establishments” is not expressly defined but limited by the closed delineation provided in Recital 20 which declares the exception applicable to “educational establishments recognised by a Member State, including those involved in primary, secondary, vocational and higher education.”

Therefore, the exception seems to only contemplate formal educators as beneficiaries, this is, educational establishments responsible for primary to tertiary education, and nationally recognised as such⁶⁶. This means that non-formal educators, this is, other institutions that provide educational activities such as courses, workshops, and lifelong learning in later life are, in principle, not given the opportunity to conduct these activities in a cross-border online settings, since there is rarely an overlap between the national recognition of educational establishments and cultural heritage institutions.

One of the most prevalent examples of non-formal educators that make it a part of their mission to provide such educational opportunities to the public is that of cultural heritage institutions. They are responsible for a large portion of the non-formal education offered to the public, as their mission is not only that of preserving culture, but promoting it, validating the intrinsic tie between culture and the education of the public.

Recital 22 uses activities in a “museum, library or another cultural heritage institution” as an example for the application of the exception, yet explicitly states that only activities carried out under the responsibility of educational establishments qualify: this means that, while the activity is being promoted in the context of a formal, primary to tertiary educational setting, it can be conducted online, but if the same cultural heritage institutions provides their own workshops and learning programs, they cannot benefit from the exception. Such learning programs are, as mentioned, a rather common occurrence as institutions are not merely instruments to be used by formal educators, but an educational outlet in themselves.

4.2.2. Element 3: Cross-border uses and secure learning environments

Article 5(3) states that the use of works for the sole purpose of illustration for teaching through secure electronic environments undertaken in compliance with the requirements for the application of the exception are deemed to occur “solely in the Member State where the education establishment is established”. This means that digital uses made over a secure environment are not tied to the territory of the user, but always presumed to occur in the country of establishment of the educational facility⁶⁷ – a useful legal fiction that suppresses uncertainty regarding the cross-border scope of Article 5.

As for the requirement for secure learning environments, Recital 22 defines those as “digital teaching and learning environments access to which is limited to an educational establishment’s staff and to pupils or students enrolled in a study programme, in particular through appropriate

⁶⁶ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁶⁷ Giulia Dore, Marta Arisi & Roberto Caso, D5.1 Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) in EU (2021). <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5070449>> accessed 13 November 2022.

authentication procedures including password-based authentication”. The first part of the definition seems to be adequate to the goals of the exception, as it simply demands a closed infrastructure to operate in order to minimize harm to the interests of the rightsholder – as for the second half, it should be up to educational establishments to establish how such security is attained. Closed environments can be fluid and secure without necessarily relying on “password-based authentication”, but just other credentials or private communication channels, for example⁶⁸.

4.2.3. Element 4: Licensing priority

Article 5(2) introduces a carve-out to the exception, giving Member-States the possibility to completely ignore the educational exception (“Member States may provide that the exception or limitation adopted pursuant to paragraph 1 does not apply”) or bypass it in regard to particular categories and types of works (the examples given being material primarily intended for the educational market and sheet music). This possibility to either completely or partially exclude the application of the exception is dependent on the availability of “suitable licenses”. If Member States choose to make use of this option, it becomes their duty to ensure that such “suitable licenses” are available, findable, and accessible for educational establishments. Essentially, in countries where such option is implemented (e.g. Germany), educational establishments from that Member-State will not be able to rely on the exception once the content they were using for the purposes of illustration for teaching become commercially available, and licensable⁶⁹.

Recital 23 of the DSM Directive justifies the introduction of this carve-out by stating that “different arrangements, based on the implementation of the exception or limitation provided for in Directive 2001/29/EC or on licensing agreements covering further uses, are in place in a number of Member States in order to facilitate educational uses of works and other subject matter”. As such, these arrangements, established in the context the prior copyright framework would have allegedly been developed “taking into account the needs of educational establishments and of different levels of education”.

Therefore, and although the entire purpose of this mandatory exception is to harmonize the copyright framework and reduce legal uncertainty regarding cross-border educational uses, Recital 23 argues that “the arrangements for implementation can vary from one Member State to another, to the extent that they do not hamper the effective application of the exception or limitation, or cross-border uses.”. In a feeble attempt to argue that, despite the fragmentary approach, legal certainty is still prioritized, Recital 23 concludes that “Member States should specify under which conditions an educational establishment can use protected works or other subject matter under that exception and, conversely, when it should act under a licensing scheme.” – a double-layered

⁶⁸ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021)

⁶⁹ Giulia Priora, Bernd Justin Jütte & Peter Mezei, *Copyright and Digital Teaching Exceptions in the EU: Legislative Developments and Implementation Models of Art. 5 CDSM Directive (2022)* IIC 53, 543–566, <<<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40319-022-01179-6>>> accessible 14 November 2022.

approach to the use of copyrighted content for educational content that seems to only exist to keep the patchy state of national implementations as it is⁷⁰.

Apart from the general idea that the mere possibility to replace an exception that follows a public policy interest and allows for non-competitive and non-exploitative uses is harmful in itself, this option brings other perils to legal certainty and the fair balancing of interests in the internal market. Self-regulatory and profit-based solutions cannot be said to be a replacement for a policy-based exception: licensing terms can be exploitative, both from a financial point of view, creating pressure on the educational sector, and from a general perspective, introducing conditions that burden students and teachers alike, that now have to deal with a fragmentary and infinite set of contracts and agreements just to proceed with their normal activities⁷¹.

To introduce all of these carve-outs, giving a myriad of options to Member States to further fragment the copyright landscape seems inconsistent with the objectives of the Digital Single Market Strategy. At the bottom line, the three-step test, which is analysed in bigger detail in sub-section 4.5, exists for a reason – to assure that the application of exceptions and limitations is fair, specific to the necessary and foreseen contexts, and not detrimental to the activities of rightsholders. That should be enough in itself to assure the protection of the interests of rightsholders and call for no further measures that put legal certainty at stake.

4.2.4. Element 5: Compensation for rightsholders

Article 5(4) states that Member States may “provide for fair compensation for rightsholders for the use of their works or other subject matter”. This is an optional requirement that Member States may introduce and, according to Recital 24, in “setting the level of fair compensation, due account should be taken, inter alia, of Member States’ educational objectives and of the harm to rightsholders”.

It is quite hard to comprehend why this possibility is even offered, especially considering the fact that Article 5 is not only an exception subject to the three-step test (as detailed in the section on Article 7), which, in itself, already fulfils the role of balancing the public interest objectives (in this case, educational) of an exception with the interests of rightsholders, but also an exception for a use that is not competing with the exploitation done by rightsholders, and already restricted by *several* barriers in terms of quantity, list of beneficiaries, and security standards⁷².

⁷⁰ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁷¹ Paul Keller, Explainer: What will the DSM directive change for cultural heritage institutions? (2019) Europeana Pro, <<https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Publications/Explainer_%20What%20will%20the%20DSM%20directive%20change%20for%20cultural%20heritage%20institutions_%20090619.pdf>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁷² COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

Application of the Evaluative Matrix to Article 5 of the DSM Directive:

i) Cultural diversity:

The exception does not contemplate cultural heritage institutions as beneficiaries. An increase in the visibility, accessibility, or dissemination of European culture to the public (including the fore) is not directly foreseeable from its application. Granted that it allows educational establishments to virtually collaborate with CHIs, this is an instrumental and secondary use of cultural goods, the contribution of which cannot be said to create better conditions for the creation or access to cultural content in Europe.

ii) Adaptation to the cross-border environment:

Article 5 expands the scope of the established exceptions on educational uses to the online setting by allowing such uses to be performed on secure platforms. It enables cross-border education and reduces friction with territoriality rules.

iii) Legal certainty regarding technological developments:

The digital transition of education has brought a high level of uncertainty regarding compliance with the applicable framework. On the one hand, the exception effectively tackles this uncertainty by introducing a clear framework for cross-border education. However, all the carve-outs available for Member States to optionally deploy result in fragmentation of the (educational) eco-system and are therefore detrimental towards legal certainty. Finally, legal certainty regarding territoriality is well-established since a legal fiction in Article 5(3) allows all uses performed over a secure electronic environment to be considered to occur in the country of establishment of the educational institution.

iv) Cultural creative reuse:

No reuse is allowed. The provision only allows the beneficiaries to share works or portions of works on a secure digital environment. The exception is limited to this layer, in the sense that pupils or other teachers cannot further engage with the digitally disseminated materials.

v) Balance of rights:

The provision does not benefit cultural heritage institutions. If the scope of application was extended to embrace non-formal educators, it would still be fair to deem it in favour of rightsholders: apart from reasonable steps to keep a balance between public and private interests, such as demanding a secure channel of communication, a source and the author's name to be mentioned⁷³, the exception is extremely limited by somewhat disproportionate barriers: regardless of the fact that the three-step is applicable and that the uses allowed by the exception are non-

⁷³ The European Copyright Society, Comment of the European Copyright Society Addressing Selected Aspects of the Implementation of Articles 3 to 7 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 on Copyright in the Digital Single Market (2020), <<https://europeancopyrightsociety.org/2022/05/03/https-europeancopyrightsocietydotorg-files-wordpress-com-2022-05-ecs_exceptions_final-1-pdf/>> accessed 14 November 2022.

competing with the rightsholder's, Article 5 also provides Member States with the option to demand compensation for educational uses and to exclude or limit certain subject matter.

4.3. Preservation of Cultural Heritage (Article 6)

Introduction and Context

Article 6 of the DSM Directive, titled “Preservation of Cultural Heritage”, establishes an exception to various rights provided for in different Directives, for purposes of preservation of cultural heritage.

Within the framework of Article 6, entirely centred on reproductions for purposes of cultural heritage preservation, Member States are mandated to introduce an exception to the author’s exclusive right to carry out temporary or permanent reproduction by any means and in any form, in whole or in part of a copyright protected database (Article 5(a) of Directive 96/9/EC, on the legal protection of databases), and to the exclusive right of the author of a sui generis database to extract or reuse parts or the entirety of the contents of that database (Article 7(1) of Directive 96/9/EC, on the legal protection of databases.). Additionally, the same exception shall also apply to the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit direct or indirect, temporary, or permanent reproduction by any means and in any form, in whole or in part of an author or rightsholder’s work or protected subject matter (Article 2 of Directive 2001/29/EC), as well as to the reproduction of computer programs (Article 4(1)(a) of Directive 2009/24/EC on the legal protection of computer programs)⁷⁴. Finally, Article 6 also creates an exception to the exclusive rights concerning the online use of press publications (reproduction and communication to the public), as delineated in Article 15 of the DSM Directive.

Simply put, if a cultural heritage institution wishes to create a copy of a work or subject matter permanently held in their collections for purposes of and to the extent necessary for the preservation of those works, they can rely on Article 6, which creates an exception to the exclusive rights of reproduction of copyrighted databases, authorial works, other protected subject matter, computer programs and online press publications, and to the exclusive right of extraction of a sui generis database⁷⁵.

4.3.1. Element 1: Scope of the exception

The exception introduced by Article 6 of the DSM Directive essentially exempts the beneficiaries from requiring an authorization to perform various acts of reproduction. The exception covers acts of reproduction of works, fixations of performances, phonograms, fixations of films, fixations of broadcasts, computer programs, databases protected by copyright and press publications, and the temporary or permanent reproduction, in whole or in part of databases protected by sui generis rights.

⁷⁴ Marie-Christine Janssens, Arina Gorbatyuk, & Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, Deliverable 2.1: Mapping of the relevant European IP legal framework (2021), <<<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141439>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁷⁵ Giulia Dore, Marta Arisi & Roberto Caso, D5.1 Report on the existing legal framework for Galleries and Museums (GM) in EU (2021). <<<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5070449>>> accessed 13 November 2022.

The application of the exception is not subject to the payment of any kind of compensation⁷⁶ and copies can be made in any format or medium, using any appropriate tool, means or technology, with no upstream restriction on how the preservation is carried out, as long as the task is focused on this purpose. Furthermore, there is no limitation on how many copies can be made, as this is determined by the required extent for the fulfilment of the preservation goal.

4.3.2. Element 2: Purpose limitation

As previously pointed out, Article 6 highlights that the exception applies only “for purposes of preservation of such works or other subject matter and to the extent necessary for such preservation.”. This idea is complemented by the text of Recital 27 which exemplifies preservation tasks “to address technological obsolescence or the degradation of original supports or to insure such works and other subject matter.”. However, the second part of Recital 27 clearly states that the exception should “allow the making of copies (...) at any point in the life of a work or other subject matter” which means that, while the degradation of the work or other protected subject matter surely complies with the purpose limitation, it does not need to occur, as institutions can choose to preventively make copies of any material in their collection in order to preserve it⁷⁷. Similarly, the list of examples provided is not exhaustive, and the concept of “preservation” should be interpreted broadly: as long as the task intends to or results in the prolonging of the subsistence or availability of the work, it should be classified as a preservation task.

The final part of Recital 27 states that other acts of reproduction “for purposes other than the preservation of works and other subject matter in their permanent collections should remain subject to the authorisation of rightholders, unless permitted by other exceptions or limitations provided for in Union law.”. This means that, within the context of this particular exception, the utilization of digitisation technologies is merely authorized if the objective or result of the task are to preserve a work or other protected subject matter⁷⁸.

4.3.3. Element 3: Permanency of work in collection

The text of Article 6 explicitly mentions that these copies for preservation purposes can only be performed on “works or other subject matter that are permanently in their collections”. While, traditionally, in a pre-digital era, it would be fairly easy to categorize works as being “in” the collection of an institution, that is not the case anymore as particular temporary licensing modalities that technically grant unlimited access to works in third-party servers have become common

⁷⁶ Although some countries, like Belgium, have implemented remuneration schemes. See: Giulia Priora & Caterina Sganga, D5.2 Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU (2021), <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621049>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁷⁷ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁷⁸ João Pedro Quintais, The New Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive: A Critical Look (2020), European Intellectual Property Review 42(1), 28-41, <<<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3424770>>> accessed 14 November 2022.

practice, but do not seem to fall under the definition of “permanent ownership”, particularly due to the weight put on the concept of a “collection”.

Recital 29 of the Directive attempts to clarify this concept of “permanency” by defining that works and other subject matter are considered to be in the collection of a CHI in a permanent manner when “copies of such works or other subject matter are owned or permanently held by that institution, for example as a result of a transfer of ownership or a licence agreement, legal deposit obligations or permanent custody arrangements”.

Another problem with the concept of permanency contends with the public availability of material on the internet. It is unknown whether such material albeit permanently available to the beneficiary complies with the requirement of “permanency”⁷⁹, but once again, the focus on the “collection” seems to suggest the contrary⁸⁰.

4.3.4. Element 4: Beneficiaries

The beneficiaries of the exception are cultural heritage institutions. As previously mentioned, the definition of what consists of a “cultural heritage institution” can be found in Article 2(3) of the DSM Directive, which defines them as publicly accessible library or museums, archives, or film and audio heritage institutions. Since CHIs serve as custodians of cultural heritage, it is only natural that they would be the core beneficiaries of the exception. However, and according to Recital 13 of the DSM Directive, “Cultural heritage institutions (...) should also be understood to include, inter alia, (...) and, as far as their archives and publicly accessible libraries are concerned, educational establishments, research organisations and public sector broadcasting organisations”. Therefore, the scope of beneficiaries seems to be wider than what is foreseen in Article 2⁸¹. All cultural heritage institutions “by default” (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums), and all other educational, scientific, or public interest institutions that have publicly accessible archives or libraries, can benefit from Article 6 of the DSM Directive.

4.3.5. Element 5: Intermediaries and cross-border cooperation

Having established CHIs as the beneficiaries of the exception of Article 6 of the DSM Directive, it is possible to imagine that not all institutions willing to conduct a digitisation task possess the necessary means to do so, either because equipment is usually expensive, and given the sparsity in

⁷⁹ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

⁸⁰ Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021)

⁸¹ The European Copyright Society, Comment of the European Copyright Society Addressing Selected Aspects of the Implementation of Articles 3 to 7 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 on Copyright in the Digital Single Market (2020), <<https://europeancopyrightsociety.org/2022/05/03/https-europeancopyrightsocietydotorg-files-wordpress-com-2022-05-ecs_exceptions_final-1-pdf/>> accessed 14 November 2022.

which it may be needed it may not be viable to acquire standalone equipment, or because the institutions may not have trained personnel in digitisation tasks⁸².

This is the challenge that Recital 28 of the DSM Directive attempts to address. Accordingly, if an institution does not have the “technical means or expertise to undertake the acts required to preserve their collections themselves”, they can recur to the assistance of other cultural institutions and other third parties for that purpose. This distinction between “other cultural institutions” and “other third parties” is relevant, since it explicitly enables the possibility to rely on private partnerships to conduct digitisation tasks, while still complying with the requirements of Article 6. This collaboration can be achieved in multiple ways, be it through preservation networks and shared servers, or by sharing equipment or loaning works for digitisation.

According to the second part of Recital 28, under the exception for preservation purposes, “cultural heritage institutions should be allowed to rely on third parties acting on their behalf and under their responsibility, including those that are based in other Member States, for the making of copies.”

Effectively, not only is the reliance on other CHIs and on private partnerships possible, but all of these collaborations and partnerships can be done between institutions in different Member States, in a cross-border form. Recital 26 of the Directive points out that the different national approaches to acts of preservation by cultural heritage institutions hampers the sharing of technology and knowledge among institutions, and the establishment of cross-border preservation networks, which is, ultimately, an inefficient use of resources. As such, one of the objectives of this mandatory exception is precisely to suppress such uncertainties regarding cross-border uses and mitigate the aforementioned inefficiencies⁸³.

Application of the Evaluative Matrix to Article 6 of the DSM Directive:

i) Cultural diversity:

Out of all the exceptions in Title II, Article 6 may be the one that allows for the greatest level of conservation and proliferation of cultural diversity. The reasoning is evident: although the allowed digitisation practices are not intended for making the materials available, the ultimate mission of a cultural heritage institution is to bring culture to the public. Preservation efforts will always benefit cultural diversity, even if just for the fact that the conditions for the survival of the work are assured, which means it will be accessible to the public for longer. The fairly large scope of the exception contributes to the maintenance of conditions that enable future generations to retain access to cultural assets, which ultimately, bolsters the visibility of European culture, even if not directly.

ii) Adaptation to the cross-border environment:

⁸² Paul Keller, Explainer: What will the DSM directive change for cultural heritage institutions? (2019) Europeana Pro, <<https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Publications/Explainer_%20What%20will%20the%20DSM%20directive%20change%20for%20cultural%20heritage%20institutions_%20090619.pdf>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁸³ Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021)

The promotion of cross-border preservation networks, as well as the enlarged list of beneficiaries and intermediaries allowed to participate in this preservation task is delineated in a good way to transpose the cultural preservation task to a cross-border environment.

However, the mission of cultural heritage institutions is not only accomplished through preservation tasks. In fact, digitised materials could (and would) be used for other internal purposes such as cataloguing and indexing collections. These activities can still be performed, but under the unharmonized exception of Article 5(2)(c) of the InfoSoc Directive, or through an expansive transposition of Article 6 through the mechanisms of Article 25.

Nonetheless, and while the recognition of the value of cross-border and digital preservation networks is most surely welcome, the failure to identify the value of digitised copies for a whole other myriad of internal uses seems to reflect a recognition of the benefits of adapting the copyright framework to the cross-border environment but wariness in providing a comprehensive framework for the beneficiaries beyond a purpose-limited one.

iii) Legal certainty regarding technological developments:

While the exception seems to appropriately adapt prior preservation exceptions to the availability of highly technological digitisation architectures, it seems to fail to achieve a higher level of legal certainty by perpetuating an outdated perspective on the functioning of cultural heritage institutions. Such is the case of the imposition for works to be digitised under the new exception to be in the “permanent collection” of the institutions, a concept which does not necessarily perfectly translate to the modern array of works available to institutions nor their intended purpose. The examples of the open web and of content in third-party servers, to state a few, demonstrate how institutions may have access to works in a permanent fashion that they may be interested in preserving due to the well-established instability and fleeting nature of online content, in forms other than ownership, temporary ownership, loans and deposits⁸⁴.

iv) Cultural creative reuse:

From a general perspective, the exception does not enable the creative reuse of cultural assets. The digitization tasks allowed are restricted by a purpose limitation, making any other uses subject to unharmonized copyright exceptions or the consent of the rightsholder.

However, from a wider standpoint, it is relevant to understand that a work the longevity of which has been assured has higher chances. This preservation task can pertain to a work and certainly pertains to a work that will eventually enter the public domain. Although, once that happens, the exception does not apply, as the permanency of the work could only be assured through prior preservation efforts. Therefore, it is not illogical to state that enabling a favourable copyright framework that allows works to remain available for the future may be considered a primer of creative reuse.

v) Balance of rights:

⁸⁴ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

The rights balancing exercise seems to favour the activities of cultural heritage institutions and enable the pursuit of their public mission objectives. The well-delineated scope of beneficiaries and wide range of action covered by the exception, along with the absence of an obligation of fair compensation, and a total freedom to choose the means and mediums to perform the conservation task seem to indicate that the legislator recognizes the absence of conflict between the preservation task and the interests of rightsholders.

4.4. – Common provisions (Article 7)

Introduction and Context

Article 7, simply titled “Common provisions”, establishes two separate rules regulating potential conflicts between the correct and lawful application of copyright exceptions and the enforcement of private rule, performed either through contractual impositions, or technical protection measures (TPM’s).

Taking into consideration that the provisions of Title II are intended to introduce fairly new carve-outs to the established systems of copyright protection, the clarification of the relationship between the exceptions and other contractual or technical mechanisms that may oppose to them is necessary, not only for purposes of achieving legal certainty but also conserving the fair balance between the interests of rightsholders and users. This does not mean, however, that the same solution is foreseen for contractual measures and for technical protection measures, particularly due to the fact that TPM’s are the specific subject of explicit legal protection in the European Union⁸⁵.

As such, on the one hand, according to the first part of Article 7 (Article 7.1.), any contractual provision contrary to the exceptions provided for in Articles 3, 5, and 6 is unenforceable – these are all the exceptions introduced in Title II except for Article 4, the exception for text and data mining for purposes other than scientific research.

On the other hand, Recital 7 of the DSM Directive explains that, while the protection of technological measures, as established in the InfoSoc Directive, “remains essential to ensure the protection and the effective exercise of rights granted to authors and other rightsholders”, these technological measures shall not prevent the enjoyment of the exceptions and limitations provided for in the DSM Directive⁸⁶. Article 7(2) of the DSM Directive provides the solution to this tension through a peculiar set of references to the rules on TPM protection laid out in the InfoSoc Directive.

According to Article 7(2), “Article 5(5) of Directive 2001/29/EC shall apply to the exceptions and limitations provided for under this Title. The first, third and fifth subparagraphs of Article 6(4) of Directive 2001/29/EC shall apply to Articles 3 to 6 of this Directive.”. The differential terminology used in the same provision may cause confusion, since “the exceptions and limitations provided for under this Title” (the set of exceptions contained in Title II of the DSM Directive) directly correspond to “Articles 3 to 6 of this Directive”. Simply put, the Article applies to the entirety of Title II, except for Article 7.

The first part of Article 7(2) contains nothing more than a direct reference to Article 5(5) of the InfoSoc Directive which reiterated the “three-step test”, according to which exceptions and limitations only apply “in certain special cases which do not conflict with a normal exploitation of the work or other subject-matter and do not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the

⁸⁵ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021).

⁸⁶ Anthony D Rosborough, *Unscrewing the Future: The Right to Repair and Circumvention of Software TPMs in the EU* (2020), JIPITEC 11(1), <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3693187>> accessed 14 November 2022.

rightsholder.”. This is, nonetheless, an important assertion: similar to all copyright rules since the Berne Convention, the exceptions and limitations introduced by the DSM Directive cannot escape this balancing exercise.

The second part of the Article, however, introduces a more specific rule regarding the direct relationship between the application of the exceptions and TPM protection. The direct interpretation of the Article does not immediately translate into a concrete set of rules, since it, once again, establishes its normative value by referencing the rules contained in another instrument, respectively, paragraphs 1, 3 and 5 of Article 6(4) of the InfoSoc Directive.

Paragraph 1 of Article 6(4) of the InfoSoc Directive establishes that, in the absence of voluntary measures taken by rightsholders, Member States have an obligation to ensure that these rightsholders make the means necessary to benefit from an exception or limitation available for their beneficiaries, “to the extent necessary to benefit from that exception or limitation and where that beneficiary has legal access to the protected work or subject-matter concerned.”.

Paragraph 3 counterpoints, adding that, if technological measures have been voluntarily applied by rightsholders, then these measures enjoy “adequate legal protection against the circumvention of any effective technological measures, which the person concerned carries out in the knowledge, or with reasonable grounds to know, that he or she is pursuing that objective.”.

Finally, Paragraph 5 explains that the same rules apply in the context of rental right and lending right on the legal protection of databases.

Put in a clearer way, Article 7(2) simply establishes that the three-step test (exceptions and limitations apply in certain special cases, that do not conflict with a normal exploitation of the work and do not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the rightsholder⁸⁷) applies to the exceptions and limitations in Title II, and that, if a beneficiary of an exception or limitation needs particular technical means to access and use TPM-protected content, rightsholders have the freedom to choose how to enable such access and use, and only if they refuse to, they are mandated to provide those means by the relevant authorities within Member States. Unlike the provision on contractual override, the second part of Article 7(2) does not exclude Article 4 of the DSM Directive from its scope.

4.4.1. Element 1: Scope of Contractual Override

Article 7(1) establishes that some of the exceptions of Title II of the DSM Directive prevail over antagonistic contractual terms. These contractual terms, which, assuming the validity of a contract, would otherwise be binding and enforceable, are now unenforceable if they pose any kind of barrier to the application of Articles 3, 5, and 6 of the DSM Directive⁸⁸. The term “contractual provision”

⁸⁷ Christophe Geiger, Daniel J. Gervais & Martin Senftleben, *The Three-Step-Test Revisited: How to Use the Test’s Flexibility in National Copyright Law* (2013), *American University International Law Review* 29(3), 581-626, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2356619>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁸⁸ COMMUNIA, *DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines*, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 14 November 2022.

may refer to an actual contract, signed between the user and the rightsholder, such as a licensing agreement, or passive contracts such as a website's terms and conditions, which are agreed upon by a simple click, or sometimes simply by accessing and using a website. Contractual override is transcendent to the origin, nationality, or place of establishment of the counterpart (be them a natural person or a legal person) that is restricting the application of the exception, as well as to the selected forum (the national law by which the contract is regulated), even if outside of the EU⁸⁹. As long as the user attempting to benefit from one of the foreseen exceptions or limitations is based in the EU, that contractual disposition is not enforceable.

4.4.2. Element 2: Beneficiaries of Contractual Override

Article 7(1) applies to the exceptions provided for in Articles 3, 5, and 6 of the DSM Directive. Accordingly, if a cultural heritage institution or a scientific research institution sought to perform reproductions of a work or extractions of a database to perform text and data mining for scientific research purposes, if an Educational Establishment wanted to reproduce or communicate to the public a copyrighted work without the authorization of the rightsholder for the purpose of illustration for teaching, or if a CHI wished to perform a reproduction of a protected work or other subject-matter permanently in their collection in order to preserve that work or protected subject-matter, these institutions or persons attached to could not be stopped by a contractual provision that goes against such attempts - all the new exceptions introduced in Title II that have a direct connection with the activities of cultural heritage institutions, scientific research institutions and educational establishments have prevalence over contractual provisions. This reinforces the prevalence of a regulatory perspective based on the balance of public and interests over a self-regulating approach to the internal market – copyright exceptions serve a function and are allowed based on the public mission that their beneficiaries pursue, thus overriding private ruling. Unfortunately, as stated in a prior section, this logic seems to have been constricted in certain cases, such as the introduction of optional carve-outs to the educational exception (Article 5), allowing Member States to reject the exception, introduce licensing priorities, or fair compensation obligations for users trying to benefit from the exception.

Notwithstanding, the prevalence of exceptions over contractual provisions means that if, for example, a website's terms and conditions contain either explicit provision prohibiting web-scraping or mass-data analytics⁹⁰, or an implicit restriction to the scope of the exception by enumerating a closed list of allowed uses, then those provision can be ignored by a researcher using the data on the website for text and data mining. It is important to point out that, in the case of contractual override, the rest of the contract remains enforceable, and only the particular provision that posed a barrier to the application of the exception or limitation is rendered unenforceable against the user.

Quite evidently, if the user is not complying with the conditions of the exception, then the contractual provisions prevail⁹¹. Following the earlier example, if the researcher did not obtain

⁸⁹ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021).

⁹⁰ Recital 18 of the DSM Directive.

⁹¹ Recital 18 of the DSM Directive.

lawful access to the work, and is viewing the content of the website, for example, by unlawfully breaching server access restrictions, then the exception is not applicable, and there is no conflict between exception and contract, with the terms of the latter applying fully.

Conversely, the detailed scope of Article 7(1) also means that all remaining copyright exceptions continue to be unprotected against adverse contractual terms. Within the scope of the DSM Directive, this comprises the broader exception for text and data mining established by Article 4, and any other new copyright exception not contained in Title II, particularly the exception for the lawful use of out-of-commerce works in Article 8(2) of the Directive. As such, if the previous example had a for-profit institution that had lawful access to the website attempting to scrape it for purposes of massive statistical data analytics instead of a scientific research organization, they would be effectively restricted from performing that activity in a lawful manner if the website's terms and conditions so dictated.

4.4.3. Element 3: Three-step test

The first part of Article 7(2) provides that for a user to benefit from the exceptions and limitations of Articles 3 to 6, these need to comply with the three-step test, this is, that these can only be applied in certain special cases which do not conflict with the normal exploitation of the work, and do not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the rightsholder⁹².

Although this has long been an established rule in European copyright history, three issues concerning its application can be identified: interpretation and balancing of interests, hierarchical and geographical scope of effect, and, with the introduction of Article 25 of the DSM Directive, compatibility with flexibility of implementation.

In short, the first issue contends with the intended strictness of interpretation of exceptions and limitations in the European copyright framework. While it is true that, traditionally, exceptions and limitations have been construed as special cases of derogation from the general rule that is the highest level of protection for original works and other protected subject matter, the line of reasoning that argues that exceptions and limitations, albeit conceived as such, have essentially become equivalent to user rights, and merit an equivalent high level of protection⁹³.

In fact, not only do legislatures have to assure the aforementioned high level of protection for rightsholders and the products of their labour and originality, but also the effectiveness of the exceptions and limitations – this is generally done by prioritizing the balancing of the diverse interests at stake. If that is the case, defining exceptions as only applicable when they do not conflict with the normal exploitation of works or other subject matter seems to go against the standard of effectiveness of those exceptions, and to their conceptualization as user rights – an exception will

⁹² Christophe Geiger, Daniel J. Gervais & Martin Senftleben, *The Three-Step-Test Revisited: How to Use the Test's Flexibility in National Copyright Law* (2013), *American University International Law Review* 29(3), 581-626, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2356619>> accessed 14 November 2022.

⁹³ Tito Rendas, *Are Copyright-Permitted Uses 'Exceptions', 'Limitations' or 'User Rights'? the Special Case of Article 17 CDSM Directive* (2021), *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice*, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3968252>> accessed 14 November 2022.

always hinder the normal exploitation of the work, that is what they are created for, to disrupt exclusivity and monopolistic market tendencies in detriment of the rightsholder, to the advantage of the public interest.

Ideally, the three-step test would serve merely as a self-executing balancing mechanism: regardless of whether one perceives exceptions and limitations as limited carve-outs to the standard of high copyright protection, or as independent user rights that need to be considered in conjunction with such a high standard of protection, the parameters of the three-step test should be sufficient to achieve the balance of interests, by prescribing that balancing perspective in the interpretation and implementation of the exceptions. Therefore, and considering that this mechanism should be sufficient in itself to assure the effectiveness of exceptions and limitations, one cannot help but question the need to directly regulate optional standards for Member-States to enhance copyright protection. Such is, once again, the case of Article 5: if the three-step test is intended to ensure that the rightsholder is not prejudiced by the effective and justified application of an exception, then why are Member States given the option to introduce measures intended to protect the interests of the rightsholders, such as licensing priority, fair compensation obligations, thus disrupting what would otherwise supposedly be a self-balancing environment?

As for the second identified issue, the hierarchical and geographical scope of the three-step test has long been a primer for hermeneutic debate. Devoid of any indication of who the addressees of the test are, some argue that it is a prescription for Member States in their implementation, others for national courts in their interpretation, and the generally accepted perspective is that it influences all instances of interpretation and application of the exception⁹⁴, to such an extent that it provides natural persons to invoke it against what they perceive to be disproportional restrictions on their enjoyment of their exclusive rights⁹⁵.

Finally, as was previously mentioned, Article 25 provides Member States with a margin of flexibility on the implementation of the provisions of DSM Directive, allowing them to adopt broader provisions tailored to national political objectives, as long as this enlargement is deemed compatible with the previous copyright Directives and the scope of action of the DSM Directive. The relationship between the three-step test which clearly highlights the special nature of exceptions and limitations along with the relevance of keeping its scope limited by the possibility for rightsholders to enjoy their exclusive rights, and Article 25 which creates an unparalleled possibility of stretching the fabric of these provisions to adapt them to a national context is yet to be contested and interpreted – they are not necessarily incompatible, but it is possible to project how the perks of the flexibility of the latter may impact the strictness of the former.

⁹⁴ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021)

⁹⁵ Maurizio Borghi, *Exceptions as users' rights in EU copyright law (2020) CIPPM/Jean Monnet Working Paper No. 06-2020*, <https://microsites.bournemouth.ac.uk/cippm/files/2020/10/06-2020-MBorghi_Copyright-exceptions-as-users-rights.pdf> accessed 15 November 2022.

4.4.4. Element 4: Technological override

According to Recital 7 of the DSM Directive, the protection of technological protection measures remains “essential to ensure the protection and effective exercise of the rights granted to authors and other rightsholders” which, simultaneously, should not conflict with the “enjoyment of the exceptions and limitations provided for in this Directive”. The Directive highlights that this balance should be preliminarily and voluntarily enforced by rightsholders, who “remain free to choose the appropriate means of enabling the beneficiaries of the exceptions and limitations”. Only if rightsholders choose to not take this balancing obligation into consideration by selecting not to voluntarily complement their technical protection with “appropriate means” for beneficiaries to enjoy the application of exceptions and limitations, may Member States intervene. In this scenario, Member States are not only entitled but mandated to take “appropriate measures” to ensure compliance with the effectiveness of the exceptions and limitations “in accordance with the first subparagraph of Article 6(4) of Directive 2001/29/EC”.

As previously mentioned, the first paragraph of Article 6(4) of the InfoSoc Directive states essentially the same as Recital 7 of the DSM Directive: voluntary measures are to be taken by rightsholders, otherwise statutory intervention is necessary to grant effectiveness of exceptions and limitations. However, Article 6(4) of the InfoSoc Directive delineates the scope of the “appropriate measures” to be taken by Member States if prompted to do so. Accordingly, they should provide “the means of benefiting from that exception or limitation to the extent necessary to benefit from that exception or limitation and where that beneficiary has legal access to the protected work or subject-matter concerned.” The corollary of these requirements imposed to the “appropriate measures” to be put in place by Member States is the set of criteria that the intended use by the beneficiaries of an exception have to comply with in order to be able to claim that the technical protection measures are limiting that lawful use: the technical measure has to be disproportionate to the point that it is perceived as limiting to the expected and necessary uses reliant on the exception, and legal access to the protected work is necessary.

4.4.5. Element 5: Appropriate measures

The baseline of the technological override system is that technical protection measures should not limit the effectiveness of the application of exceptions and limitations. As is the case of the provision on contractual override, and of any other balancing exercise, the possibility to create the highest level of protection for their works and protected subject-matter is given to the rightsholders – the limit of that protection, is, of course, the enjoyment of statutory public interest exceptions.

What is left to the imagination is how this balance is achieved. While technically it may seem that this obligation gives the beneficiaries of exceptions and limitations the much-needed right to legally surpass technological protection measures, all that the second part of Article 7(2) prescribes is a right to ask for appropriate measures, and not a right to access. In the end, all that a beneficiary of one of the exceptions in Title II of the DSM Directive who has lawful access to the subject matter that is protected by technological protection measure is to argue that the technical characteristics of the measure make it disproportional and mitigate the effectiveness of the exception, and request

Member States to take appropriate measure. Likewise, what these “appropriate measures” might be is also not revealed or hinted at.

While on the one hand it is perfectly reasonable that the way to deal with such access requests is left to Member States, on the other hand, it seems lacking that no guidance on this matter has been provided. Considering the fact that so many options are given to Member States when the matter at stake is the further enlargement and reinforcement of a high level of protection, the absence of an exemplary or descriptive, non-exhausting and non-enumerating list of suggestions for possible options for standard practices to harmonize expectations in a cross-border environment.

Application of the Evaluative Matrix to Article 7 of the DSM Directive:

i) Cultural diversity:

The protection of new mandatory exceptions and limitations against contractual override allows cultural heritage institutions to have a more powerful stance: considering that half of the new exceptions are conceived in benefit of the cultural sector, the fact that they cannot be limited by contract means their range of application is amplified, which may lead to better conditions for the creation and dissemination of cultural heritage.

Appropriate measures as defined in the framework for technological override herein exposed leaves a lot to be desired: as mentioned, if a beneficiary of an exception (in this analysis, a CHI) wants to make use of that exception lawfully, but faces technological restrictions, there is no immediate procedure for removal of technical protection measures, nor any complaint and redress mechanism targeted at reducing such an impediment.

ii) Adaptation to the cross-border environment:

The lack of enforcement of contractual terms that block the enjoyment of an exception or limitation indirectly benefits the adaptation to a cross-border environment if the exception is targeted towards such uses. Other than that, Article 7 does not further expand the scope of copyright rules to an online setting.

iii) Legal certainty regarding technological developments:

The provisions on technical protection measures do not account for the true complexity of digital rights management solutions and their impact on the regular and daily activities of the potential beneficiaries.

iv) Cultural creative reuse:

Article 7 has no impact on cultural reuse.

v) Balance of rights:

Apart from the application of the three-step test which is, in itself, a mechanism to ensure a proportional application of exceptions and limitations, and therefore, prioritize, or at least defend

the interests of rightsholders, Article 7 introduces two measures: contractual override and technological measures. The former seems to balance towards beneficiaries, in the sense that private ruling cannot deprive them of the uses granted by the exception; the latter may appear to also benefit beneficiaries since it is generally stated that technological protection measures shall not prevent the use of exceptions, but, as exposed, such a statement is ineffective if proper mechanisms are not prima facie established.

Ultimately, Article 7 is in itself an extended balancing exercise, so it is fair to assume balance between colliding rights and interests is assured, albeit slightly in detriment of the beneficiaries of exceptions due to the complete absence of practical mechanisms to assure the “right to appropriate measures”.

4.5. – Final assessment of Title II of the DSM Directive

Chapter 4 – Title II						General evaluation of the Article (CHI – centred)
	Fostering Cultural Diversity	Adaptation to the digital environment	Suppression of technological uncertainties	Enabling creative reuse	Fair balance of interests	
Sub-Chapter 4.1 – Text and data mining for research purposes (Article 3)						
4.1.1 – Beneficiaries and scientific research purpose	+	-	+	+	0	
4.1.2 – Scope of the exception	-	-	+	-	+	
4.1.3 – Lawful access	-	-	-	-	+	
4.1.4 – Secure storage obligations	-	-	-	0	0	
4.1.5 – Network integrity measures	-	-	-	0	0	
Assessment of Article 3:	-	-	0	0	+	0
Sub-Chapter 4.2 – Digital and cross-border teaching activities (Article 5)						
4.2.1 – Scope and beneficiaries	-	+	+	-	-	
4.2.2 - Cross-border uses and secure environments	-	+	+	-	+	
4.2.3 - Licensing priority	-	0	-	0	-	
4.2.4 - Compensation for rightsholders	-	0	-	0	-	
Assessment of Article 5:	-	+	0	-	-	-
Sub-Chapter 4.3 - Preservation of Cultural Heritage (Article 6)						
4.3.1 – Scope of the exception	+	+	+	0	+	
4.3.2 – Purpose limitation	0	-	-	-	+	
4.3.2 – Permanency of work in collection	-	-	-	0	0	

(...)						
	Fostering Cultural Diversity	Adaptation to the digital environment	Suppression of technological uncertainties	Enabling creative reuse	Fair balance of interests	General evaluation of the Article (CHI – centred)
4.3.4 - Beneficiaries	+	+	+	+	+	
4.3.5 – Intermediaries and cross-border cooperation	+	+	+	0	+	
Assessment of Article 6:	+	+	+	0	+	
Sub-Chapter 4.4 – Common provisions (Article 7)						
4.4.1 – Contractual Override (Scope)	+	+	+		+	
4.4.2 – Contractual Override (Beneficiaries)	+	0	+		+	
4.4.3 – Three-step test	0	0	-	0	0	
4.4.4 – Technological Override	+	+	-	0	0	
4.4.5 – Appropriate Measures	-	0	-	0	-	
Assessment of Article 7:	+	0	0	0	+	

Table 2 – Final assessment of Title II of the DSM Directive.

Note: *Green* means “Positive”; *Orange* means “Neutral” or “N/A”; *Red* means “Negative”. “. Overall assessment (darker shading) is performed based on the average classification of selected elements. In case of a tie or 1-point difference, priority is given to a positive assessment to avoid negative bias. Subtitles (+, 0, -) added for accessibility purposes.

5 - Title III – Measures to Improve Licensing Practices and Ensure Wider Access to Content (Articles 8 to 14)

Title III of the DSM Directive (Measures to Improve Licensing Practices and Ensure Wider Access to Content) is dedicated to the introduction of new provisions to “facilitate certain licensing practices, in particular, but not only, as regards the dissemination of out-of-commerce works and other subject matter and the online availability of audiovisual works on video-on-demand platforms, with a view to ensuring wider access to content”⁹⁶. As Recital 3 suggests, the aim of this portion of the Directive is to clarify the copyright framework regulating the dissemination of out-of-commerce works and audiovisual works, as well as “the use of content in the public domain”.

Unlike Title II, which contained the provisions relating to new mandatory exceptions and limitations, Title III is subdivided into four distinct chapters, each attempting to facilitate licensing practices in a distinct dimension. Considering that the present exposure attempts to follow the schematization of the Directive, this division will be respected and followed in this chapter.

Chapter 1 is dedicated to out-of-commerce works and other subject matter, providing a set of concrete rules and definitions for the exploitation of works no longer commercially available to the public. This chapter is directly targeted at cultural heritage institutions, and composed of Articles 8 to 11.

Article 8 (Use of out-of-commerce works and other subject matter by cultural heritage institutions), contemplates a new Extended Collective Licensing modality, a new copyright exception (which, presumably, was not included in Title II since it serves as a fallback mechanism if the conditions for the application of the licensing scheme are not gathered), conditions for voluntary exclusion (opt-out), as well as exclusions based on territoriality.

As the title of Chapter 1 indicates, all the provisions therein contained directly relate to the exploitation of out-of-commerce works by CHIs. Article 8 is undoubtedly the most complex and detailed of all, since the new licensing scheme and fallback exception are detailed in it – the three remaining Articles can be seen as serving an instrumental role⁹⁷ to the out-of-commerce works regime introduced by Article 8: Article 9 complements Article 8 by outlining rules on cross-border uses of out-of-commerce works, Article 10 establishes the necessary publicity measures as an appropriate safeguard for rightholders wanting to exclude the application of licenses or the exception to their works, and Article 11 mandates Member States to consult rightholders, collective management organisations and cultural heritage institutions in each sector before establishing specific requirements for the application of Article 8.

Chapter 2 of Title III (Measures to facilitate collective licensing) contains only one provision (albeit a long one), Article 12. Article 12, introducing a new set of rules for collective licensing with extended

⁹⁶ Recital 3 of Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC.

⁹⁷ Paul Keller, Explainer: What will the new EU copyright rules change for Europe's Cultural Heritage Institutions (2019) Europeana Pro <<https://pro.europeana.eu/post/explainer-what-will-the-new-eu-copyright-rules-change-for-europe-s-cultural-heritage-institutions>> accessed 13 November 2022.

effect, as is analysed at a later stage in this Chapter, shares its fair share of similarities with the regime contained in Article 8 in the sense that both introduce a licensing modality based on a presumption of representativity by a collective management organization, thus, not dependent on the express authorization of the rightsholder⁹⁸. Notwithstanding, two differences of major relevance need to be highlighted: Chapter 1 of Title III deals exclusively with out-of-commerce works and contemplates CHIs (as defined in Article 3 of the DSM Directive) as the sole beneficiary of its provisions while Chapter 2 contemplates any works (out-of-commerce or not) and any potential beneficiary. Furthermore, while Chapter 1 of Title III introduces a set of mandatory provisions for transposition, the choice to introduce the single provision in Chapter 2 is left to Member States.

Arguably the least relevant for the activities of cultural heritage institutions, Chapter 3 (Access to and availability of audiovisual works on video-on-demand platforms) introduces an obligation for Member States to establish or designate an impartial body of mediators dedicated to providing assistance to “parties facing difficulties related to the licensing of rights when seeking to conclude an agreement for the purpose of making available audiovisual works on video-on-demand services”.

Finally, and similarly to the two preceding chapters, Chapter 4 (Works of visual art in the public domain) introduces one provision of great relevance for the activities of CHIs, Article 14, which excludes copyright protection for faithful reproductions of works of visual art in the public domain.

⁹⁸ Giulia Priora & Caterina Sganga, D5.2 Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU (2021), <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621049>> accessed 13 November 2022.

5.1. – Out-of-commerce works (Chapter 1: Articles 8-11)

Introduction and Context

According to Recital 30 of the DSM Directive, “Cultural heritage institutions should benefit from a clear framework for the digitisation and dissemination, including across borders, of works or other subject matter that are considered to be out of commerce for the purposes of this Directive.”. However, the particular characteristics of out-of-commerce works, such as “the age of the works or other subject matter, their limited commercial value or the fact that they were never intended for commercial use”, along with the sheer amount of works used in mass digitisation projects means that obtaining prior authorization from individual rightsholders is particularly difficult. It is important to mention, at this point, that for the sole purpose of creating a digital replica of a work, Article 6 allows cultural heritage institutions to perform acts of reproduction without the authorization of the rightsholders, a point that is reinforced by Recital 43 which states that these measures implemented to facilitate collective license of rights in out-of-commerce works should be “without prejudice to the use of such works (...) under exceptions or limitations provided for in Union law” – therefore, the framework for Article 8 goes beyond mere reproductions and contemplates all (non-commercial) uses of out-of-commerce works permanently located in the collections of cultural heritage institutions.

Article 8 is divided into 7 paragraphs, comprising four “clusters” of regulation: the licensing mechanism, the fallback exception, the opt-out mechanism and the geographical rules and limitations. Article 8(1) defines the conditions for the attribution of a non-exclusive license for non-commercial purposes to a cultural heritage institution for the reproduction, distribution and communication to the public of out-of-commerce works (defined in Article 8(5); Article 8(2) introduces an exception allowing cultural heritage institutions to make available, for non-commercial purposes⁹⁹, out-of-commerce works, but, according to Article 8(3), this exception only applies when no collective management organization fulfils the conditions set out in paragraph 1. Article 8(4) establishes appropriate safeguards for authors and rightsholders who “may, at any time, easily and effectively, exclude their works or other subject matter from the licensing mechanism set out in paragraph 1 or from the application of the exception or limitation provided for in paragraph 2”. Article 8(6) and 8(7) lay out specific rules and carve-outs dependent on the location of the CHI, and the international provenance of the out-of-commerce work. Because each paragraph is connected to one of the aforementioned “clusters” to a specific degree, this division will be used to dissect the vast array of rules established in Article 8. Due to their aforementioned instrumental level, Articles 9, 10 and 11 will be respectively assigned to the clusters on territoriality, safeguards, and the licensing mechanism.

5.1.1. – Scope and definitions (Articles 8(5) and 11)

a) Out-of-commerce works

⁹⁹ Giulia Priora & Caterina Sganga, D5.2 Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU (2021), 11 <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621049>> accessed 13 November 2022.

According to Article 8(5) of the DSM Directive, a “work or other subject matter shall be deemed to be out of commerce when it can be presumed in good faith that the whole work or other subject matter is not available to the public through customary channels of commerce, after a reasonable effort has been made to determine whether it is available to the public.”. This definition is complemented by Recital 37, which clarifies they can be any type of work, such as “photographs, software, phonograms, audiovisual works, and unique works of art, including where they have never been commercially available. Never-in-commerce works can include posters, leaflets, trench journals or amateur audiovisual works, but also unpublished works or other subject matter”. Article 8(1) clearly defines the bulk of pieces that can be exploited through the new set of rules as consisting only of “works or other subject matter that are permanently in the collection of the institution”. In this case, this concept is less of a problem than in the case of Article 6, in which reproductions of works online could be considered relevant for the purposes of preservation. For purposes of dissemination of digitized materials, the definition of “works permanently in the collection of the institution”, this is, works “owned or permanently held by that institution, for example as a result of a transfer of ownership or a licence agreement, legal deposit obligations or permanent custody arrangements.” (Recital 29), is less problematic.

In the sense of the definition of “out-of-commerce”, works that cannot be found in “customary channels of commerce”, or put in another way, works that cannot be considered to be generally widely available to the public¹⁰⁰, should be considered out-of-commerce works. It is, however, important to mention that when the work is still available in different versions, editions or formats, it should not be considered to be out-of-commerce – Recital 37 seems to contemplate the materiality of the work for the purposes of determining its “out-of-commerce” status, considering subsequent editions or updated formats to be the same work as the original piece in the sense that the availability of one version precludes the possibility of using the others under this framework. While it is certainly easy to agree that the work contained in an e-book and the work contained in a physical copy of a book are the same, and if one format is still commercially available, then the work itself is “in-commerce”, the subject of different editions is a particularly complex and controversial one: for the purposes intended by the introduction of this regime, this is, to make works confined in the collections of CHIs available to the public, it would be more useful to consider, for example, a first edition to be distinct from further editions – more often than not, these differences between versions and subsequent editions are the core subject of study by the ones interested in obtaining access to them¹⁰¹. And yes, while researchers can still access the work on dedicated terminals in-premise (Article 5(3)(n) of the InfoSoc Directive)¹⁰², this defeats the digital availability purpose of the out-of-commerce works framework. Conversely, adaptations and translations are considered to be

¹⁰⁰ Giulia Priora & Caterina Sganga, D5.2 Report on the existing legal framework for Libraries and Archives (LA) industries in EU (2021), <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4621049>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹⁰¹ Rita Matulionyte, Copyright in Published Editions: A History of a Declining Right (2019), Monash University Law Review 45(1), <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3490994>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹⁰² Arina Gorbatyuk, Marie-Christine Janssens & Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, Deliverable 2.2: Legal comparative analysis for multi-level relationship involving CHIs (2021) <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141536>> accessed 13 November 2022.

independent works, and their availability does not “preclude a work or other subject matter from being deemed to be out of commerce in a given language.”¹⁰³.

Notwithstanding, the concept of “customary channels of commerce” is left undefined¹⁰⁴, although some guidance is provided on the matter. According to Recital 38, the “limited availability of a work or other subject matter, such as its availability in second-hand shops, or the theoretical possibility that a licence for a work or other subject matter could be obtained” is not to be considered as a sign of widespread availability to the public in customary channels of commerce: it is not because you could technically or hypothetically obtain a copy if you knew where to look for that it can be considered to be commercially available – as mentioned above, this concept is deeply grounded on an idea of widespread availability, or general availability to a member of the public.

b) Additional requirements and stakeholder dialogue

Furthermore, the second part of Paragraph 5 of Article 8 states that “Member States may provide for specific requirements, such as a cut-off date”, this is, according to Recital 37, “a requirement for a certain time period to have elapsed since the work or other subject matter was first commercially available”. The development of specific requirements may be necessary due to “specificities of different types of works and other subject matter as regards modes of publication and distribution, and to facilitate the usability of those mechanisms”.

According to Article 11, and in order to ascertain the relevance and usability of the mechanisms introduced by the out-of-commerce works framework, as well as to conserve appropriate safeguards for rightsholders, Member States are mandated to hold consultations with rightsholders, collective management organizations and cultural heritage institutions before establishing any of these additional requirements set out in Article 8(5).

c) Reasonable effort

According to Recital 38 of the Directive, the determination of the out-of-commerce status should be subject to a reasonable effort to “assess their availability to the public in the customary channels of commerce, taking into account the characteristics of the particular work”. This reasonable effort does not have to involve “repeated action over time” but it should consider any evidence of the upcoming availability of the. Similarly, it is not necessary to perform a work-by-work assessment, except when relevant information is available. This effort should also take place in the Member State where the cultural heritage making use of the work is established unless it is reasonable to expect cross-border verification, for example when it is evident that the work was first published in another Member State.

¹⁰³ Recital 37 of Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC.

¹⁰⁴ Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021)

This nuanced concept of “reasonable effort” seems to counter the “diligent search” requirement set out in Article 3 of the Orphan Works Directive¹⁰⁵ which obligated organizations to perform an often transnational thorough search for the author of the work before being allowed any use, and to maintain accurate records of their searches – a set of requirements generally considered to be too stringent and burdensome, responsible for delaying the licensing process and creating more barriers to mass digitization efforts than viable avenues¹⁰⁶.

5.1.2. Licensing mechanism (Article 8(1))

a) Extended Collective Licensing and Presumption of Representation

The mechanism introduced in Article 8(1) allows sufficiently representative Collective Management Organizations (CMOs) to grant licenses to CHIs on behalf of rightsholder that have “not mandated a representative collective management organisation in that regard” (Recital 31). Therefore, and “irrespective of whether all rightsholders covered by the license have mandated the collective management organization”, the CMO is allowed to conclude a license with a CHI for the reproduction, distribution, communication to the public or making available to the public of out-of-commerce works.

The two conditions for this provision to operate are that: the CMO is considered to be sufficiently representative (Article 8.1.a) and that all rightsholders are “guaranteed equal treatment in relation to the terms of the license” (Article 8.1.b), meaning that all rightsholders are considered equally in the licenses, regardless of whether they are actually represented by the CMO.

The rights covered by the license are broad but well-defined: a license issued by a sufficiently representative CMO to a CHI can cover “reproduction, distribution, communication to the public or making available to the public”¹⁰⁷.

b) Non-exclusive, non-commercial

Article 8(1) indicates that these licenses negotiated by collective management organisations are non-exclusive and for non-commercial purposes. This means that, if the CMO is considered to be sufficiently representative, the fact that it has negotiated a licensing agreement with a CHI cannot preclude it from negotiating licenses with other CHIs.

¹⁰⁵ “For the purposes of establishing whether a work or phonogram is an orphan work, the organisations referred to in Article 1(1) shall ensure that a diligent search is carried out in good faith in respect of each work or other protected subject-matter, by consulting the appropriate sources for the category of works and other protected subject-matter in question. The diligent search shall be carried out prior to the use of the work or phonogram.” Article 3 of Directive 2012/28/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on certain permitted uses of orphan works.

¹⁰⁶ Simone Schroff, Marcella Favale & Aura Bertoni, *The Impossible Quest – Problems with Diligent Search for Orphan Works* (2017) IIC - International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition 48, pages 286–304.

¹⁰⁷ Arina Gorbatyuk, Marie-Christine Janssens & Sonsoles Pajares Rivas, *Deliverable 2.2: Legal comparative analysis for multi-level relationship involving CHIs* (2021) <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141536>> accessed 13 November 2022. (2021) <<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5141439>> accessed 13 November 2022.

The “non-commercial” element of the license must also be correctly conceptualized: Recital 40 indicates that the uses covered by the licenses should not generate profit, “including where copies are distributed by the cultural heritage institution, such as in the case of promotional material about an exhibition.” However, and “given that the digitisation of the collections of cultural heritage institutions can entail significant investments, any licences granted under the mechanism provided for in this Directive should not prevent cultural heritage institutions from covering the costs of the licence and the costs of digitising and disseminating the works“. It is therefore clear that the generation of revenue is not a problem, since CHIs are at least allowed to cover licensing, digitization, and dissemination costs by engaging in economical exploitation of the work – if this exploitation becomes targeted towards generating profit, however, that is against the terms of Article 8(1) and most probably against the license terms.

c) Sufficiently representative

The types of licenses that allow a CMO to act on behalf of rightholders not represented by them work possibly under a presumption of representation. A CMO is considered to be sufficiently representative in this context when two conditions are simultaneously met: a sufficient number of rightholders in the sector must be represented by the CMO; a significant number of rightholders must have mandated the CMO to negotiate licenses for one, some, or all of the rights listed in Paragraph 1, and subject of the license. As such, it is not enough that “a significant number” of rightholders in the field are represented, it is required that the CMO actually holds relevant mandates for the rights concerned¹⁰⁸.

Furthermore, and according to Recital 33, “Member States should also have flexibility in determining what the requirements for collective management organisations to be sufficiently representative are, as long as that determination is based on a significant number of rightholders in the relevant type of works or other subject matter having given a mandate allowing the licensing of the relevant type of use.”. For the purpose of this mechanism, CMOs should follow the particular rules on good governance, transparency, reporting and payment distribution present in in Directive 2014/26/EU (Recital 34)¹⁰⁹.

The licenses issued by CMOs should not only cover the rights intended, but also the purposes requested. A CMO that is sufficiently representative on the basis of rightholder of a specific type of subject matter, for example, cinematographic works, but that only has mandates from those

¹⁰⁸ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹⁰⁹ “In order to enhance the trust of rightholders, users and other collective management organisations in the management of rights by collective management organisations, each collective management organisation should comply with specific transparency requirements. Each collective management organisation or its member being an entity responsible for attribution or payment of amounts due to rightholders should therefore be required to provide certain information to individual rightholders at least once a year, such as the amounts attributed or paid to them and the deductions made. Collective management organisations should also be required to provide sufficient information, including financial information, to the other collective management organisations whose rights they manage under representation agreements.” Directive 2014/26/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights in musical works for online use in the internal market.

rightsholders to grant the right to communicate to the public for specific purposes might not be sufficiently representative to grant the right of making available online for an out-of-commerce work.

5.1.3 – Fallback exception (Article 8(2) and 8(3))

a) Conditions for application

Sufficient representativity is essential for CMOs to be able to enter into a licensing agreement for out-of-commerce works without directly representing the rightsholder. However, and as Recital 32 indicates, there may be cases in which “there is no practice of collective management of rights for a certain type of work or other subject matter or where the relevant collective management organisation is not sufficiently representative for the category of the rightsholders and of the rights concerned.”. In such scenarios, the CHI would be essentially left without any option except to individually negotiate licenses and obtain authorizations for each of the works concerned.

If that is the case, CHIs can rely in the exception introduced in Article 8(2) which allows them to make out-of-commerce works or other subject matter permanently in their collections available, for non-commercial purposes, on the condition that “(a) the name of the author or any other identifiable rightsholder is indicated, unless this turns out to be impossible; and (b) such works or other subject matter are made available on non-commercial websites.”.

Article 8(2) limits the scope of the exception to “the rights provided for in Article 5(a), (b), (d) and (e) and Article 7(1) of Directive 96/9/EC, Articles 2 and 3 of Directive 2001/29/EC, Article 4(1) of Directive 2009/24/EC, and Article 15(1) of this Directive”¹¹⁰.

It is therefore evident that the scope of the exception is fairly more limited than that of the licensing mechanism. While the licensing mechanism simply authorizes all acts related to the work or subject matter, the exception purposely excludes the distribution right from its scope. The distinction is particularly relevant when dealing with authorial works: while the licensing mechanism allows a CHI to seek a license for any, many or all of the three rights (reproduction, distribution, communication to the public), according to the intended purposes, the exception is meant to enable digital accessibility after digitization efforts only. On the one side, a CHI that obtains a license for the works in their collection based on the fact that these are not available in the customary channels of commerce, is engaging in a licensing process that is purpose-limited (they can negotiate a license for the reproduction of out-of-commerce works although that’s heavily advised against since that activity is covered by the exception in Article 6; they can negotiate a license for the distribution of those works to disseminate them physically) – in this licensing process they pay what is considered to be an appropriate licensing fee for the uses covered, the scope of rights contained in Article 8(1) is just indicative of which rights can be negotiated for the intended purpose.

¹¹⁰ This is, respectively, all the rights concerning copyrighted databases (reproduction, translation, adaptation, arrangement, distribution, communication) and sui generis databases (extraction and reutilization), the rights of reproduction and communication to the public of copyrighted works (but notably, not the right of distribution), all the exclusive rights granted to the author of a computer program (reproduction, translation, adaptation, arrangement, alteration, distribution), and press publisher rights.

On the other hand, the exception is a limitation on the power of the rightsholder to retaliate against the use of their work without their authorization, which, as is indicated in a further section, is not subject to remuneration¹¹¹. Therefore, and regarding authorial works, the exception seems to only grant a right to reproduce (digitize) and communicate to the public (post online) as opposed to the right to use other avenues to disseminate when in the possession of a proper license with a sufficiently representative CMO.

b) Availability of licensing solutions, lack of agreement and “licensing lockout”

According to Article 8(3), the exception in paragraph 2 “only applies to types of works or other subject matter for which no collective management organisation that fulfils the condition set out in point of paragraph 1 exists”. As was analysed already, if a collective management organization for a particular type of work does not exist, or if it exists but does not have sufficient rightsholders in the relevant type of works and of the rights that are the subject of the license, or if the CMO refuses to negotiate a licensing deal, then a “sufficiently representative” CMO does not exist¹¹². However, what is the solution in case a sufficiently representative CMO and the CHI seeking to obtain a license cannot reach an agreement? Can the CHI rely on the exception since they could not obtain a license?

The answer would be negative. If there is a sufficiently representative CMO, then there is an availability of licensing solutions – that is the real requirement for the application of the exception¹¹³. As Recital 32 puts it, “uses under such exception or limitation only take place when certain conditions, in particular as regards the availability of licensing solutions, are fulfilled. A lack of agreement on the conditions of the licence should not be interpreted as a lack of availability of licensing solutions.”. This means that a smaller bargaining power against suboptimal licensing offers may effectively lock the CHI out of a licensing agreement unless they comply with the sufficiently representative CMO’s terms, since the existence of those terms implies the availability of licensing solutions. This is a good sign for CHI’s that hold particular subject matter that does not have much collective management representation (like video games¹¹⁴) since they can rely on the exception almost directly due to a lack of a sufficiently representative CMO, but less positive for CHI’s attempting to make use of works pertaining to an artistic field characterized by very high representation rates (like music¹¹⁵) which may lead to even lower bargaining power and higher licensing rates. Notwithstanding, as previously mentioned CMOs are bound by specific duties under Directive 2014/26, such as the obligation to conduct negotiations in good faith, draft licensing terms

¹¹¹ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹¹² Tatiana Synodinou, The New Copyright Directive: Out of commerce works (Articles 8 to 11): is it possible to untie the Gordian knot of mass digitisation and copyright law without cutting it off? – Part II (2019), Kluwer Copyright Blog, <<http://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2019/08/05/the-new-copyright-directive-out-of-commerce-works-articles-8-to-11-is-it-possible-to-untie-the-gordian-knot-of-mass-digitisation-and-copyright-law-without-cutting-it-off-part-ii/>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹¹³ Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021) 197.

¹¹⁴ Tori Allen, What's in a Game: Collective Management Organizations and Video Game Copyright (2018) UNLV Gaming Law Journal 8(2), Article 8 <<https://scholars.law.unlv.edu/glj/vol8/iss2/8>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹¹⁵ Mihail Miller, Stephan Klingner, Transparency Reports of European CMOs: Between legislative aspirations and operational reality – comparability impending factors and solution strategies, 13 (2022) JIPITEC 160 para 1

based on objective and non-discriminatory criteria and select tariffs for exclusive rights in a reasonable manner in relation to their real economic value¹¹⁶ – all of these may attenuate the aforementioned difference in bargaining power.

c) Compensation and three-step test

Regarding the application of the exception, there is no indication of whether it should be subject to remuneration or not¹¹⁷ – this question is particularly contentious, as some experts argue that, in light of the fact that the Directive does not indicate whether the exception is remunerated or not, and considering it only applies when there is not a representative CMO, there is no mechanism to distribute remuneration fees amongst rightsholders¹¹⁸, which means it is not subject to remuneration, while other experts claim the exact opposite, that the lack of indication means it should be treated generally and may be subject to remuneration¹¹⁹. The arguments for the first position seem to be more convincing in the sense that the silence of the legislative drafting body seems to be deliberate – otherwise, the conditions for remuneration would be indicated or referenced. Furthermore, Recital 35 of the Directive, which provides additional detail on the opt-out-mechanism (described in the next section) for rightsholders mentions that the use of the opt-out mechanism does “not affect their claims to remuneration for the actual use of the work or other subject matter under the licence.”. The fact that only the license is mentioned as leading to remuneration reinforces the point that remuneration of the rightsholder does not exist when there is no CMO involved and no mechanism to distribute it.

Another quarrelsome question is whether the three-step test, which is normally applicable to all exceptions and limitations in the copyright acquis applies to Article 8(2). On the one side, some experts argue that the three-step test is exceptionally not applicable since Article 7(2) of the DSM Directive, which mandates that exceptions in the DSM Directive be subject to the three-step test,

¹¹⁶ Articles 16(1) and 16(2) (Licensing) of Directive 2014/26/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights in musical works for online use in the internal market Text with EEA relevance.

¹¹⁷ LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries), Mass Digitisation Of Published & Unpublished Out-Of-Commerce Works. <<https://zenodo.org/record/3529039/files/Mass%20Digitisation%20of%20OOC%20Works.pdf?download=1>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹¹⁸ Ariadna Matas and Paul Keller, authors of the Chapter on Articles 8-11 of the COMMUNIA Guidelines on the Implementation of the DSM Directive argue that “While the intention of the lawmaker was for this exception to be unremunerated, the directive does not indicate whether the exception is remunerated or not, and none of the recitals clarify this. In practical terms, it seems that the exception should be unremunerated as it only applies in the absence of a representative CMO, which means that there won’t be a mechanism to distribute the remuneration to rightsholders.”. COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹¹⁹ According to Professor Eleonora Rosati, “in the context of Article 8 the qualification as ‘exception’ or ‘limitation’—in practice— means that Member States are entitled to envisage a compensation requirement. Although Article 8 is silent on the issue of compensation, this conclusion is supported by the treatment of the other exceptions or limitations in the Directive (see in particular *infra* ‘Article 5’);”. Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021) 197.

does not reference Article 8(2)¹²⁰. This argument, like the previous one, is merely technical in nature since it does not provide any particular reasoning for precluding the application of the three-step test to this exception¹²¹. However, it can be further argued that, because this is an exception meant to work as a subsidiary scenario in the lack of proper conditions to proceed to licensing, it is dissimilar to other exceptions in the sense that it is not justified only by the purpose intended (which is, on first layer, achieved by the licensing mechanism) nor by the public mission of the beneficiary alone, and thus all the conditions of the three-step test are already achieved by the framework of the exception itself: the “certain special cases” are defined by the exception in the sense that it is only applicable in the lack of licensing availability; the exception does not conflict with the normal exploitation of the work and does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author because, as examined in the next section, provisions on appropriate safeguards for authors are a part of the out-of-commerce works regime as well.

5.1.4 – Safeguards (Articles 8(4) and 10)

a) Opt-out mechanism

According to Recital 35, appropriate safeguards to protect rightsholders should be available – in the case of out-of-commerce works, rightsholders “should be given the opportunity of excluding the application of the licensing mechanisms and of the exception” in relation to all or specific works in use, licenses or uses. This “modularity” of the opt-out mechanism deserves considerable praise since it allows rightsholders to only oppose to the components of the framework that they do not agree with – instead of a general exclusion of the license or exception, a license can be conserved without the excluded elements, and the application of the exception can be retained without the excluded uses. This power can be used at any time before or during the term of the license or the use of the exception. Relevantly enough, and due to possible practical consequences, ongoing uses do not need to be terminated immediately, but within a “reasonable period”. Finally, the exclusion by rightsholders should not affect their claims to remuneration for the use of their work under the license – as pointed out in the previous section, this Recital also implies that uses through the exception are not to be remunerated. All these principles laid out in Recital 35 are directly connected to Article 8(4) of the DSM Directive, which states that “rightsholders may, at any time, easily and effectively, exclude their works or other subject matter from the licensing mechanism set out in paragraph 1 or from the application of the exception or limitation provided for in paragraph 2, either in general or in specific cases, including after the conclusion of a licence or after the beginning of the use concerned.”

¹²⁰ The authors of the Chapter on Articles 8-11 of the COMMUNIA Guidelines on the Implementation of the DSM Directive, Ariadna Matas and Paul Keller, argue that “Member States do not have to apply the EU three-step test, laid down in article 5(5) of the InfoSoc Directive, to this exception. Article 7(2) makes the test applicable to some of the new copyright exceptions, but not to this one”

¹²¹ As Professor Eleonora Rosati argues: “The Directive does not say whether the exception or limitation in 8(2) leaves unprejudiced and does not affect the application of the three-step test. Even lacking specific wording (cf. Article 7) there is no reason to think that the three-step test in Article 5(5) of the InfoSoc Directive 2001/29 and other relevant EU directives would not apply to Article 8(2)”. Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021) 201.

b) Publicity measures

Quite evidently, for a rightholder to be able to oppose to the use granted through extended collective licensing, or being made under the prerogative of the exception for out-of-commerce works, they need to be aware that this use is being made. Recital 41 states that all information regarding planned or ongoing use of out-of-commerce works by CHIs on the basis of the DSM Directive, as well as the possibility to oppose to the licensing mechanism and exception should “be adequately publicised both before and during the use under a licence or under the exception or limitation”.

Article 10 (Publicity Measures) of the DSM Directive introduces some rules to achieve this correct and timely information by mandating Member States to ensure that all information from CHIs, CMOs and other relevant authorities concerning the identification of out-of-commerce works being used and covered by the licensing mechanism or the exception for out-of-commerce works, as well as “information about the options available to rightholders as referred to in Article 8(4)”, parties of the license, uses and territories covered is “made permanently, easily and effectively accessible on a public single online portal from at least six months before”.

c) Further publicity measures

In addition to making this information available through the portal, it may be necessary to engage in further action to make rightholders aware that the granting of licenses by CMOs and the use of exceptions by CHIs is now a possibility. Article 10(2) suggests that “if necessary for the general awareness of rightholders, additional appropriate publicity measures are taken regarding the ability of collective management organisations to license works (...), the licenses granted, the uses under the exception (...) and the options available to rightholders”. Furthermore, and according to Recital 41, the “necessity, the nature and the geographic scope of the additional publicity measures should depend on the characteristics of the relevant out-of-commerce works or other subject matter, the terms of the licences or the type of use under the exception or limitation, and the existing practices in Member States.”. These publicity measures, however, should be done through communication channels that have the potential to reach rightholders, and not on an individual basis.

5.1.5 – Territoriality (Articles 8(6), 8(7) and 9)

a) Country of establishment (licensing, commercial availability, publicity)

Article 8(6) states that “Member States shall provide that the licences referred to in paragraph 1 are to be sought from a collective management organisation that is representative for the Member State where the cultural heritage institution is established.”. This concept of “country of establishment” is profusely used in the out-of-commerce works, albeit lacking a concrete definition.

Not only is the concept of “country of establishment” relevant for the access to licensing options, which can only be sought in said territory, but also for determining the availability of the work in customary channels of commerce, and to define additional publicity measures. Regarding the former, Recital 38 asserts that the verification of availability of a work takes place in the Member

State where the “cultural heritage institution is established”, unless the repetition of this search across borders is considered to be reasonable and relevant, “for example in cases where there is easily available information that a literary work was first published in a given language version in another Member State”. As for the latter, the second paragraph of Article 10(2) mentions that the additional appropriate publicity measures that may be required to inform rightholders of the use of their work “shall be taken in the Member State where the licence is sought” (which, by default, is the country of establishment of the CHI) and, “for uses under the exception or limitation provided for in Article 8(2), in the Member State where the cultural heritage institution is established”. However, if there is significant evidence to “suggest that the awareness of rightholders could be more efficiently raised in other Member States or third countries, such publicity measures shall also cover those”.

All in all, the concept of “country of establishment” is relevant to determine where the license is sought, to determine the availability of the work, as well as the range of additional appropriate measures. This concept should be interpreted broadly and according to pre-existent EU Law and CJEU case-law¹²² – accordingly, and in the case of legal persons such as cultural heritage institutions, “a permanent presence in the Member State in question comes within the scope of the provisions of the Treaty on the Right of Establishment, even if that presence does not take the form of a branch or agency, but consists merely of an office managed by the undertaking’s own staff or by a person who is independent but authorized to act on a permanent basis for the undertaking.”¹²³. Therefore, a CHI is considered to be established in a Member State when it holds permanent presence in that Member State, regardless of how this permanent presence is assured. The main establishment does not need to be present in the Member State, nor does it need to have its main physical premises located within that Member State.¹²⁴

b) Exclusion of works from third countries

If the aforementioned reasonable effort to determine the commercial availability of the work yields a negative result, the territory of first publication or establishment of the author can still influence the application of Article 8, leading to its inapplicability. According to Article 8(7), if there is evidence that a set of what would be considered out-of-commerce works consists predominantly of: “(a) works or other subject matter, other than cinematographic or audiovisual works, first published or, in the absence of publication, first broadcast in a third country; (b) cinematographic or audiovisual works, of which the producers have their headquarters or habitual residence in a third country; or (c) works or other subject matter of third country nationals, where after a reasonable effort no Member State or third country could be determined pursuant to points (a) and (b).”, then the EU out-of-commerce works framework is not applicable, and CHIs cannot pursue a license nor rely on the exception. Regarding these reasonable efforts, Recital 39 determines that a “work-by-work assessment of the origin of out-of-commerce works or other subject matter should only be required

¹²² Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021) 171.

¹²³ Paragraph I.A.2 of the COMMISSION INTERPRETATIVE COMMUNICATION, Freedom to provide services and the general good in the insurance sector (2000/C 43/03).

¹²⁴ Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021) 171.

insofar as it is also required for making the reasonable effort to determine whether they are commercially available.”. In conclusion, if there is significant evidence that a set of works predominantly consist of works of third countries (determined through the criteria of first publication, first broadcast, headquarters, habitual residence or, subsidiarily, nationality of the author), they cannot be used under the licensing mechanism or the exception.

Nonetheless, this exclusion does not apply if the CMO is considered to be sufficiently representative for a third country (Article 8(7), second paragraph). According to Recital 39, this can happen via a representation agreement, for example.

c) Cross-border uses

Taking into consideration that one of the core objectives of the DSM Directive is to enable the potential of the digitization of European cultural heritage, one can expect the new set of provisions to be adapted to a cross-border digital environment (as seen in the previous chapter, which demonstrated that cross-border collaboration and even cross-border applicability of exceptions was present in most if not all of the new mandatory exceptions). Such is also the case with the new out-of-commerce works framework. According to Recital 41, “Contracting cultural heritage institutions and collective management organisations should remain free to agree on the territorial scope of licences¹²⁵, including the option of covering all Member States”. This guarantee is repeated in the first paragraph of Article 9 (Cross-border uses). The key takeaway is that a license can, as demonstrated, be celebrated with a CMO from a Member State in which the CHI can be considered to be “established”. That (sufficiently representative) CMO is the body celebrating the licensing agreement on behalf of the rightsholder (represented or not), but the license can cover uses (such as distribution and communication to the public) in other Member States.

The same strategy does not apply to the same extent when the use of the exception in Article 8(2) is concerned: according to Article 9(2), the uses of out-of-commerce works under the exception “shall be deemed to occur solely in the Member State where the cultural heritage institution undertaking that use is established.”. This is, of course, nothing but a legal fiction since the right of communication to the public, in the context of publishing works online, has a cross-border range¹²⁶. Therefore, the permitted use (as outlined before, communication to the public only) is legally considered to happen solely in the Member State where the CHI is established, but in practice may have cross-border effects in all EEA member states.

Application of the Evaluative Matrix to Chapter 1 of Title III of the DSM Directive:

i) Cultural diversity:

The new framework for out-of-commerce works allows cultural heritage institutions in the possession of works that are not commercially available to the public to digitize, distribute and

¹²⁵ Comment of the European Copyright Society on the Implementation of the Extended Collective Licensing Rules (Arts. 8 and 12) of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 on Copyright in the Digital Single Market.

¹²⁶ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

disseminate those works. By default, the sheer possibility of taking works stuck in largely inaccessible archives or collections, and making them available to the general public can be considered to be a net positive for cultural diversity in the sense that such a framework definitely has the potential to increase the visibility of and access to European Culture.

The fact that the new regime is framed in the context of “mass digitization”, and that, for the licensing mechanism all three assignable economic rights (reproduction, distribution and communication to the public) can be negotiated with a CMO, and, in the case of the exception, the making available right, which most times will be exploited through acts of dissemination over the internet, can be used by a benefitting cultural exception greatly reinforces the point that one of the predicted intended uses is indeed to deploy those works in an online environment, accessible to members of the public, be them citizens of the European Union, or “the fore”.

While the new provisions do not necessarily create better conditions for cultural creation within Europe, they certainly address the outcome of a problem directly tied to the correct exploitation of the Union’s immense cultural diversity. Of course, the effective impact of this framework on cultural diversity will also depend on how Member States implement the new rules: as an example, a very broad definition of what a “sufficiently representative” CMO consists of may lead to overly representative organizations, and, consequently, to failed licensing negotiations and “licensing lockout” - good implementation should therefore rely on a strict definition of representativity¹²⁷, allowing CHIs to make effective use of the exception, and to make works available to the public.

Overall, the combined impact of Articles 8 to 11 of the DSM Directive on the promotion of cultural diversity and enablement of dissemination practices is a strong positive: works from European authors that the general public would otherwise not have access due to their unavailability in customary channels of commerce can now be easily found and enjoyed.

ii) Adaptation to the cross-border environment:

The new set of rules may seem a bit stringent on what can classify as an out-of-commerce work. From the perspective of a non-territorial, dematerialized online space, requirements on the country of establishment of the CHI seeking a license and the CMO that can grant it, as well as the exclusion of works from third countries creates a dependence on an idea of nationality. Furthermore, and as is further detailed in subsection v) on the creative reuse of works, this set of rules is not necessarily fully prepared to embrace common uses in an online setting, in the sense that reuse is a core component of online dynamics in the present day.

Nevertheless, the range of application of the licensing mechanism and the exception can actually be perceived as beneficial for the dilution of barriers in the dissemination, access, and flow of cultural content between European Member-States: Recital 41 and Article 9 allow CHIs and CMOs to freely agree on the territorial scope of the licenses, which includes the option of covering all Member States; Article 9(2) establishes that uses done under the exception are considered to occur in the Member-State where the cultural heritage institution is established, but, as explained, this is not

¹²⁷ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

particularly relevant, as Article 8(2) only contemplates the making available of works on a non-commercial website, which is, by virtue, cross-border in nature.

Overall, Articles 8 to 11 can be considered to be a respectable advance in the adaptation of the copyright framework to the digital environment.

iii) Legal certainty regarding technological developments:

Broadly speaking, no new technology or new use of a technology is regulated by the new framework. The out-of-commerce works regime does, however, provide an additional layer of certainty regarding the potential uses that cultural heritage institutions that invest in digitization technology may make of the works in their collections. In that regard, Articles 8 to 11 can be considered marginally beneficial for the suppression of legal uncertainty surrounding the developments in the field of digitization technology.

iv) Cultural creative reuse:

As has already been established, the out-of-commerce works framework has the potential to validate efforts of mass digitisation and support the dissemination of digitized collections to the public, thus enabling the digital availability of those works. Nonetheless, those clear advantages do not necessarily impact the possibility of culture reuse. In fact, the provisions enabling the digitization and dissemination of out-of-commerce works are quite clear about their scope: cultural heritage institutions are allowed to exploit works in their collections that can, in good faith, and after reasonable efforts, be considered to be unavailable through customary channels of commerce. And that is the end of it – the members of the public are now able to access and enjoy those collections thoroughly, but they cannot further disseminate them online (although they might be able to redistribute physical materials due to the exhaustion of the distribution right), nor subject them to creative reuse and remix, or adapt them in any way. For the members of the public, or even the cultural heritage institution themselves to be able to have any further creative power of the work, they would have to seek direct authorization from the rightsholder or rely on other exceptions that may allow them such uses.

The reasoning behind this restriction can be attributed to four factors, although the real answer is not explicit or evident, since reuse and remix rights are wholly unaddressed by harmonizing copyright instruments: firstly, the framework's goals seem to be limited to "unblocking" works in collections by simply making them available, a noble purpose on its own. Bargaining into other areas of copyright law, and further bending the interests of rightsholders could have unwarranted effects in the Union's attempt to maintain a stable and functioning internal market; secondly, and even if the right to remix and adapt a work creatively was not to be concerned, simply allowing the public to further disseminate out-of-commerce works could pose a threat to the intended functioning of the opt-out mechanism. While, in the case of a license, a CMO knows which CHI it has negotiated with, and, in both the case of the licensing mechanism and the exception, information about the use and user are published in the out-of-commerce works online portal, expanding this set of rights to a potentially infinite public would render the opt-out mechanism useless, as such a large number of uses would be impossible to track, let alone control; thirdly, considering the right to adapt is an unharmonized copyright topic, introducing an extended collective licensing mechanism and an

operating exception allowing public exploitation of that right could potentially go against the author's right to integrity, in the sense that both of these mechanisms were devised for self-contained usage prerogatives; finally, if a second layer of use were to be predictable when issuing a license to a cultural heritage institution, all further uses would need to be accounted for, driving the complexity of the licensing process and size of subsequent fees to unsustainable levels.

In conclusion, the new out-of-commerce works framework does not allow the newly disseminated works to be reused for other purposes¹²⁸ by the benefiting CHI (since the concrete uses need to be accounted for in the licence, and the exception only contemplates making the work available online) nor by members of the public (since they are not parties in the licensing agreement, nor beneficiaries of the exception), neither does it allow CHIs nor members of the public to engage in creative reuse of the content.

v) Balance of rights:

Articles 8-11 establish a brand-new range of licensing options for works in the collections of cultural heritage institutions, as well as a mandatory exception that allows them to still engage in the intended uses without authorization from the rightsholders. These are two mechanisms previously unavailable to these institutions that were clearly devised with their interests in mind¹²⁹.

It is therefore evident that the general public greatly benefits from the expanded access to cultural works. Apart from that, the other stakeholders being prioritized are cultural heritage institutions – the new framework is specifically targeted at allowing this party to use in-copyright works in a way they previously were not able to fulfil their mission.

However, the compromise between the colliding interests of CHIs wanting to fulfil their public mission of bringing culture to the public, and of rightsholders desiring to protect their intellectual property and exploit it as necessary, seems to be correctly established, albeit with some administrative burdens to CHIs: a refurbished framework for the dissemination of works not available to the public is implemented while simultaneously offering the rightsholders a robust safeguards package which attempts to ensure that they are notified or at least able to access information about the uses being made in the most efficient manner, as well as the right to oppose to these uses, terminate them within reasonable time and still get compensated for them.

¹²⁸ “While according to the Directive the cultural heritage institution can share the item online but cannot authorise any further reuse, it should be noted that users of digital cultural heritage might be able to benefit from exceptions to copyright through which they can use this material, for example for citation purposes, research or teaching.” Europeana Working Group on Out of Commerce Works, Out of Commerce Works FAQs: the system in practice (2022), Europeana Pro <<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/out-of-commerce-works-faqs-the-system-in-practice>>

¹²⁹ Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021)

5.2. – Collective licensing with an extended effect and negotiation mechanism (Ch. 2 and 3: Articles 12 and 13)

Introduction, context, and exclusion

As will become evident from the analysis developed in the present section, Articles 12 and 13 do not share similarities: the former presents new licensing mechanisms based on presumption of representation (similar to Article 8) and the latter an obligation to establish mediation bodies and mechanisms to solve conflicts in the licensing process for audiovisual works in the context of video-on-demand systems. However, not all of the provisions of the Directive are crucially relevant for the daily activities of cultural heritage institutions – Articles 12 and 13 are an example of that. In this chapter, the scope of those Articles is briefly outlined for continuity reasons, but they are not subject to the evaluative matrix due to the aforementioned relative insignificance to the activities of CHIs.

5.2.1. – Collective licensing with an extended effect (Article 12)

Article 12 establishes that a licensing agreement for the exploitation of works conducted and promoted by a CMO can be extended to apply to rightsholders that have not authorized that CMO to represent them – in this case, the organisation is presumed to represent the rightsholders who have not authorized the organisation accordingly. Paragraph 2 of the Article restricts such a licensing mechanism to “well-defined areas of use, where obtaining authorisations from rightsholders on an individual basis is typically onerous and impractical to a degree that makes the required licensing transaction unlikely, due to the nature of the use or of the types of works”. This segment highlights why the licensing mechanism is not particularly relevant for or rather, aimed at cultural heritage institutions: it is available for sectors in which licensing is onerous or impractical to a degree where it is almost impossible¹³⁰ (which is not the case for cultural heritage institutions) and targeted at Member States that want to maintain or introduce systems of collective licensing with extended effect.

Article 12(3) provides for some safeguards similar to those of the out-of-commerce works regime, namely the requirement for sufficient representativity, equal treatment of rightsholders, opt-out mechanisms and appropriate publicity measures.

5.2.2. – Negotiation mechanism (Article 13)

Article 13 establishes a negotiation mechanism for parties struggling to reach an agreement for the purpose of making available audiovisual works on video-on-demand services which “shall provide assistance to the parties with their negotiations and help the parties reach agreements, including, where appropriate, by submitting proposals to them.”. According to Recital 51, the availability of

¹³⁰ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021)

such works, in particular European works, on video-on-demand services remains limited due to licensing issues, for example when a “holder of the rights for a given territory has a low economic incentive to exploit a work online and does not license or holds back the online rights, which can lead to audiovisual works being unavailable on video-on-demand services”. Supporting negotiations would therefore facilitate legal availability of works, foster the European audiovisual sector, and fight illegal access to content.

5.3. – Works of Visual Art in the Public Domain (Chapter 4: Article 14)

Introduction and context

Article 14 of the DSM Directive obliges Member States to assert that any material resulting from an act of reproduction of a work in the public domain is not subject to copyright or related rights, unless the material resulting from such reproduction is sufficiently original in the sense that it is “the author’s own intellectual creation”. This provision works as a barrier against the unjustified and undue extension of intellectual property protection of works that should no longer enjoy such protection¹³¹, and as a harmonizing measure for inconsistent national treatments of non-original reproductions¹³².

5.3.1. – Scope and beneficiaries

There is not a concrete beneficiary of the provision per se, but it is clear that it targets cultural heritage institutions, considering the vast number of faithful reproductions of works that the processes of mass digitization entail¹³³.

It is, however, important to distinguish between claiming exclusivity and merely capitalizing on a work: Recital 53 explicitly mentions that Article 14 “should not prevent cultural heritage institutions from selling reproductions, such as postcards.”. What is being restricted is the appropriation of exclusivity via copyright over something that is no longer subject to exclusive rights (through copyright notification, reserving copyright, stating ownership, etc.).

5.3.2. – Public Domain

According to Recital 53, the “expiry of the term of protection of a work entails the entry of that work into the public domain and the expiry of the rights that Union copyright law provides in relation to that work.”. Not only is the public domain tied to the expiration of the copyright term, but also to the lack of originality: what is indeed at stake in digitized copies is their absolute lack of originality as faithful reproductions of the work, a process that is defined by the technical result and not the creative effort put in place by the performer of such digitization.

¹³¹ Andrea Wallace & Ariadna Matas, Keeping digitised works in the public domain: how the copyright directive makes it a reality (2020) *Europeana Pro*, <<https://pro.europeana.eu/post/keeping-digitised-works-in-the-public-domain-how-the-copyright-directive-makes-it-a-reality>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹³² The European Copyright Society, Comment of the European Copyright Society on the Implementation of Art. 14 of the DSM-Directive 2019/790, 11 (2020) *JIPITEC* 110 para 1, <<https://www.jipitec.eu/issues/jipitec-11-2-2020/5103>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹³³ Andrea Wallace & Ellen Euler, Revisiting Access to Cultural Heritage in the Public Domain: EU and International Developments (2020) *IIC* 51, 823–855, <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40319-020-00961-8>> accessed 13 November 2022.

5.3.3. – Works of visual art

The scope of Article 14 is limited only to “works of visual arts” – while it can surely be argued that the public domain is composed of every type of work and not only “visual art”, it is also clear that this concept was used to target a problem that could arise particularly due to digitization initiatives for visual works promoted by cultural heritage institutions¹³⁴.

5.3.4. – Public Sector Information and Public-Private Partnerships

Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast) introduced a set of rules to “address the remaining and emerging barriers to a wide re-use of public sector and publicly funded information across the Union, in order to bring the legislative framework up to date with the advances in digital technologies and to further stimulate digital innovation” (Recital 3).

Recital 65 establishes that “libraries, museums and archives hold a significant amount of valuable public sector information resources, in particular since digitisation projects have multiplied the amount of digital public domain material.”. Therefore, and according to the interpretation of Article 1(2)(j) of the PSI Directive, documents held by libraries, including university libraries, museums, and archives, are considered public sector information.

According to Recital 49 of the PSI Directive, “Where an exclusive right relates to digitisation of cultural resources, a certain period of exclusivity might be necessary in order to give the private partner the possibility to recoup its investment. That period should, however, be limited to as short a time as possible in order to comply with the principle that public domain material should stay in the public domain once it is digitised.”. This Article conveys a distinct interpretation from the clear mandate of Article 14.

Article 12(3) adds that “where an exclusive right relates to the digitisation of cultural resources, the period of exclusivity shall in general not exceed 10 years.”, and “the public sector body concerned shall be provided free of charge with a copy of the digitised cultural resources as part of those arrangements. That copy shall be available for re-use at the end of the period of exclusivity.”.

On the one side, it seems that the provisions of the PSI Directive intend to achieve the same result as Article 14 of the DSM Directive in the sense that it is made clear that public sector information, particularly cultural assets in the public domain, should be freely made available to the public for use and reuse. Notwithstanding, the compatibility of the caveat authorizing exclusivity for investment recouping may prove to be incompatible with the restrictions of Article 14.

¹³⁴ COMMUNIA, DSM Directive Implementation Guidelines, <<https://www.notion.so/DSM-Directive-Implementation-Guidelines-45233be9c0e143338860ae5a03118bf3>> accessed 13 November 2022.

Application of the Evaluative Matrix to Chapter 1 of Title III of the DSM Directive:

i) Cultural diversity:

The prohibition of exclusivity over non-original faithful reproductions of visual works of art can have significant impact in increasing the visibility, accessibility, and dissemination of European culture – with the widespread adoption of mass digitization efforts by cultural heritage institutions on its way, a safeguard of the public domain is more than welcome. Works with an expired copyright term belong to the public, and should be accessed by the public at any time without any barriers. As such, Article 14 can be considered to have positive impact in the promotion of cultural diversity.

ii) Adaptation to the cross-border environment:

The redaction of Article 14 is directly tailored at mass digitization efforts in the digital age: if these reproductions do not attract copyright protection, it is evident that they can be freely disseminated only, which greatly bolsters their digital availability and the flow of cultural content between European Member-States.

iii) Legal certainty regarding technological developments:

The provisions of Article 14 clarify the legal status of reproductions, now performed in great quantities through efforts of mass digitization. However, the joint application of Article 14 of the DSM Directive and Article 6 of the PSI Directive is still subject to a certain degree of legal uncertainty

iv) Cultural creative reuse:

Article 14 is, arguably, the provision in the DSM Directive that most contributes to the promotion of cultural reuse. Accordingly, the prohibition of unlawful appropriation of visual works with an expired copyright term through non-original reproductions allows for greater availability of cultural goods to the public, and allows these cultural assets to be subject to creative reuse, commercial or non-commercial.

That is the nature of the public domain: it belongs to the public, and that same public does not need to seek authorizations, licensing agreements or an applicable exception or limitation to be able to adapt, remix and reuse the work in question, nor exploit it however they see fit.

v) Balance of rights:

There is not a clear conflict of interests in the context of Article 14: the authors or rightsholders whose works belong in the public domain do not have the ability to protect it, and cultural heritage institutions effectuating mass digitisations of works are now able to fulfil their public mission by allowing access to these works. The institutions interested in recouping the investment in the digitisation infrastructure may still rely freely on merchandising or on the provisions of the PSI Directive.

One thing is certain: the public greatly benefits from this availability, and, in the context of the fulfilment of cultural goals, that can always be claimed as a fair balance.

5.4 – Final assessment of Title III of the DSM Directive

Chapter 5 – Title III						
	Fostering Cultural Diversity	Adaptation to the digital environment	Suppression of technological uncertainties	Enabling creative reuse	Fair balance of interests	General evaluation of the Article (CHI – centred)
Sub-Chapter 5.1 – Out-of-commerce works (Chapter 1: Articles 8-11)						
5.1.1 – Scope and Definitions (Article 8(5) and 11)	0	-	+	0	+	
5.1.2 – Licensing mechanism (Article 8(1))	+	+	0	-	+	
5.1.3 – Fallback Exception (Article 8(2) and 8(3))	+	+	0	-	+	
5.1.4 – Safeguards (Articles 8(4) and 10)	0	0	0	-	+	
5.1.5 – Territoriality (Articles 8(6), 8(7), and 9)	+	-	0	0	0	
Assessment of Article 8:	+	0	0	-	+	+
Sub-Chapter 5.2 – Works of Visual Art in the Public Domain (Chapter 4: Article 14)						
5.2.1 – Scope and beneficiaries	+	+	+	+	+	
5.2.2 – Public Domain	+	+	0	+	+	
5.2.3 – Works of Visual Art	-	+	-	+	+	
5.2.4 – Public-Private Partnerships	+	+	-	-	0	
Assessment of Article 14:	+	+	-	+	+	+

Table 3 – Final assessment of Title III of the DSM Directive.

Note: Green means “Positive”; Orange means “Neutral” or “N/A”; Red means “Negative”. “. Overall assessment (darker shading) is performed based on the average classification of selected elements. In case of a tie or 1-point difference, priority is given to a positive assessment to avoid negative bias. Subtitles (+; 0, -) added for accessibility purposes.

6 - Title IV – Measures to achieve a well-functioning marketplace for copyright (Articles 15 to 23)

Title IV of the DSM Directive introduces many relevant measures to regulate and ameliorate the existing copyright frameworks and achieve a well-functioning marketplace for copyright. Regardless of the relevance of the provisions contained within, the majority of Title IV is not applicable to cultural heritage institutions, nor does it affect their activities. As such, and for the purpose of this analysis they will not be fully dissected, as the evaluation matrix cannot be applied.

Section 6.1 of the present chapter briefly introduces Articles 15 (press publisher rights) to 17 (use of protected content by online content-sharing service providers), presenting their scope and justifying why these do not contemplate cultural heritage institutions, the main focus of the present document, as beneficiaries.

Section 6.2 tackles Chapter 3 (fair remuneration in exploitation contracts of authors and performers) which contains some provisions focused on improving the negotiation and licensing power of authors and performers by establishing several safeguards on rights to remuneration, transparency regarding usage of the licensed work as well as two contract adjustment mechanisms. In spite of not having CHIs as beneficiaries, these mandatory provisions protecting the role of authors and performers in the copyright marketplace are binding and apply to CHIs and are prone to influence the way they conduct licensing processes with rightsholders.

6.1. – Rights in publications and uses of protected content by online services (Chapter 1 and 2: Articles 15 to 17)

6.1.1. – Publisher Rights (Article 15 and 16)

According to Article 15(1) of the DSM Directive, “Member States shall provide publishers of press publications established in a Member State with the rights provided for in Article 2 and Article 3(2) of Directive 2001/29/EC for the online use of their press publications by information society service providers.”. The concept of “publishers of press publications” is new¹³⁵ and embraces service providers, such as “news publishers or news agencies, when they publish press publications within the meaning of this Directive.” (Recital 55). The concept of “press publication” is also a newly introduced one, which, according to Recital 56 should be defined “so that it only covers journalistic publications, published in any media, including on paper, in the context of an economic activity that constitutes a provision of services under Union law”.

In order to classify as a press publication, three requirements presented in Article 2(4) (Definitions) need to be fulfilled: the “publication” must be “a) an individual item within a periodical or regularly updated publication under a single title, such as a newspaper or a general or special interest

¹³⁵ Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021) 258.

magazine” with the purpose of “b) (...) providing the general public with information related to news or other topics”, that has been published in “c) (...) any media under the initiative, editorial responsibility and control of a service provider.”. For this effect, publications such as scientific or academic journals are not considered to fulfil these requirements, and cannot be considered to be press publications¹³⁶. According to Recital 56, the protection of press publications should also not apply to “websites, such as blogs, that provide information as part of an activity that is not carried out under the initiative, editorial responsibility and control of a service provider, such as a news publisher.”.

Therefore, it seems obvious that, to qualify as a press publisher, the service provider needs to do that under their own initiative and editorial responsibility¹³⁷. The main activity of cultural heritage institutions is, as pointed out repeatedly, to guard, preserve and bring to the public artifacts and works. In this sense, it might be true that a cultural heritage institution may have an editorial division in charge of producing news content “of special interest” to provide the public with information about cultural topics. However, that division is not a cultural heritage institution in itself, it is a press publisher constituted for the purpose of delivering news about cultural content, and associated to a cultural heritage institution. The distinction is, therefore, apparent – the press publisher rights will not influence the daily activities of CHIs, and, therefore, will not be further scrutinized.

Article 16 also introduces an interesting set of rules regarding the publishers’ (this time, not restricted to press publishers but also literary, scientific, and musical¹³⁸) right to a share of the rightsholders’ compensation for the use of the work under an exception or limitation. The logic behind this new right to claim fair compensation is noteworthy: Recital 60 claims that “publishers make an investment with a view to the exploitation of the works contained in their publications and can in some instances be deprived of revenues where such works are used under exceptions or limitations”, but, in some Member States, the compensation for the use of certain exceptions and limitations is not only owed to the author, but also to the person or legal person that has obtained the authors’ rights by means of contractual agreements or statutory provisions. As such, Article 16 is merely but an authorization for “Member States that have existing schemes for the sharing of compensation between authors and publishers to maintain them.”.

For the purposes of Article 16, a cultural heritage institution does not seem to fit in the definition of a publisher (in the same line of reasoning as with press publisher rights, a CHI may engage in publishing activities through a dedicated division, but that field is a publisher and not a CHI, and vice-versa). Furthermore, Article 16 does not seem to affect the activities of CHIs: under such compensation sharing schemes, the compensation potentially owed by a user or licensee (like a CHI) is, in principle, the same, just shared among the two concerned parties.

¹³⁶ Richard Danbury, 'The DSM Copyright Directive: Article 15: What? – Part II' (Kluwer Copyright Blog, 29 April) <<http://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2021/04/29/the-dsm-copyright-directive-article-15-what-part-ii/>> accessed 12 November 2022.

¹³⁷ Eleonora Rosati, Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790 (Oxford University Press 2021) 259 and 261.

¹³⁸ João Pedro Quintais, 'The New Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive: A Critical Look' [2020] 42(1) European Intellectual Property Review, page 16, <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3424770>> accessed 12 November 2022.

6.1.2. – Online Content-Sharing Providers (Article 17)

Article 17 is perhaps one of the most well-known (and definitely the longest) set of provisions stemming from the DSM Directive. It provides a thorough set of rules regulating online uses of protected content by online content-sharing service providers (in short, OCSSPs). According to Article 2(6) (Definitions), an online content-sharing service provider is a “provider of an information society service of which the main or one of the main purposes is to store and give the public access to a large amount of copyright-protected works or other protected subject matter uploaded by its users, which it organises and promotes for profit-making purposes.”.

The main takeaway from this definition is that an OCCSP is a service provider dedicated to hosting publicly accessible content online for profit-making purposes (a commonly used example of what could potentially qualify as an OCSSP for the purposes of Article 17 is video hosting platform YouTube¹³⁹). According to Recital 62, “such services should not include services that have a main purpose other than that of enabling users to upload and share a large amount of copyright-protected content with the purpose of obtaining profit from that activity.”. Article 2(6) complements this idea by declaring that other service providers such as “not-for-profit online encyclopaedias, not-for-profit educational and scientific repositories, open-source software-developing and-sharing platforms, (...) and cloud services that allow users to upload content for their own use, are not ‘online content-sharing service providers’ within the meaning of this Directive.”.

It is, therefore, evident, from this extensive definition, that a cultural heritage institution does not qualify as an OCSSP¹⁴⁰, which means that most of the rules in Article 17 are not applicable to them. However, it is still relevant to explore the implications of the new framework in two separate scenarios: when the CHI uploads to an OCSSP, and is therefore, qualified as a user of the platform, and when a work to which a CHI holds the rights to is uploaded to the platform. For this purpose, some of the obligations of OCCSPs need to be explored in a non-exhaustive and partial analysis of Article 17.

According to Article 17(1), OCSSPs perform an act of communication to the public when they allow public access to copyright-protected works uploaded by its users. As such, they should obtain the relevant authorizations from rightsholders, which, by default, also cover the platforms’ users (Article 17(2)). In the lack of authorization, OCSSPs are liable for unauthorized acts of communication to the public (Article 17(4)) unless they are able to demonstrate they made best efforts to obtain an authorization, to ensure the unavailability of the work in infringement, and acted expeditiously when notified about the infringement. Article 17(9) mandates Member States introduce “an effective and expeditious complaint and redress mechanism that is available to users of their

¹³⁹ Felix Reda, Joschka Selinger (GFF – Society for Civil Rights), ‘YouTube/Cyando – an Important Ruling for Platform Liability – Part 1’ (Kluwer Copyright Blog, 1 July) <<http://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2021/07/01/youtube-cyando-an-important-ruling-for-platform-liability-part-1/>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹⁴⁰ Federico Ferri, ‘The dark side(s) of the EU Directive on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market’ [2021] 7(7) China-EU Law Journal <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12689-020-00089-5>> accessed 12 November 2022.

services in the event of disputes over the disabling of access to, or the removal of, works or other subject matter uploaded by them”.

In conclusion, if a user uploads a work that the CHI has obtained the rights to, and that it has not authorized to be communicated in that way, the OCSSP in which the particular work was uploaded is liable for infringement of the CHIs right to communication to the public.

That is, unless they have also previously obtained a license or authorization from them, or if they comply with the exemption in Article 17(4). Alternatively, if a CHI uploads material they hold the rights to and it is unjustly flagged and removed, they should be entitled to access to effective and expeditious complaint and redress mechanisms.

6.2. – Fair remuneration in exploitation contracts of authors and performers (Chapter 3: Articles 18 to 23)

Introduction and Context

Articles 18 to 23 present a wide-ranging set of measures devised with the best interests of authors and performers in mind – these measures do not necessarily benefit CHIs, but they affect their licensing operations to an extent.

Similarly to the provisions in Chapter 1, the provisions in Chapter 3 are protected against contractual override – Article 23 states that “any contractual provision that prevents compliance with Articles 19, 20 and 21 shall be unenforceable in relation to authors and performers.”. This is particularly relevant as it means that the safeguards for appropriate and proportionate remuneration present in Article 18 can actually be contractually repealed.

Additionally, Article 21 allows the transparency obligation under Article 19 and contract adjustment mechanism under Article 20 to be submitted to a voluntary alternative dispute resolution procedure for “authors and performers are often reluctant to enforce their rights against their contractual partners before a court or tribunal” (Recital 79).

6.2.1. – Appropriate and proportionate remuneration (Article 18)

Article 18 establishes an obligation for Member-States to ensure that authors and performers are entitled to receive appropriate and proportionate remuneration when they license or transfer the exclusive rights for the exploitation of their works. This transference of exclusive rights is traditionally what occurs when a cultural heritage institution negotiates a license for the rights to a piece to be acquired¹⁴¹, and wants to exploit the piece beyond the uses permitted by exceptions and limitations. According to Recitals 72 and 73, authors and performers are usually in a weaker contractual position and their remuneration should be “be appropriate and proportionate to the

¹⁴¹ Fred Truyen & Rasa Bočyte, Deliverable 3.2: Guidelines for CHIs Digital Transformation (V.1) (2021), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5666910> accessed 13 November 2022.

actual or potential economic value of the licensed or transferred rights, taking into account the author's or performer's contribution to the overall work”, as well as other factors such as market practices or the intended uses and actual exploitation of the work.

The Directive does not exclude the practice of acquiring rights through a lump sum payment (probably because of the possibility to still engage the contractual adjustment mechanism later on) but states it should not be the rule¹⁴². The practical consequence for CHIs is the awareness that Article 18 grants authors and performers more bargaining power, and may introduce new mechanisms including collective bargaining.

6.2.2. – Transparency obligation (Article 19)

The new provisions on transparency obligations are increasingly more complex than the fair remuneration ones: Article 19 introduces 6 paragraphs, detailing the different layers of this obligation.

The first paragraph mandates Member States to ensure that authors and performers receive at least once a year, if not more frequently, actualized, relevant and comprehensive information on how their works and performances are being exploited by the licensees or sub-licensees, in particular “as regards modes of exploitation, all revenues generated and remuneration due” in order to be able to assess the economic value of their rights, compared to the remuneration received for their licence or transfer. According to recital 75, such information should be “relevant to the exploitation of the work or performance, and comprehensive in a way that it covers all sources of revenues relevant to the case, including, where applicable, merchandising revenues.”. Such an obligation, however, does not arise when “the author or performer has granted a licence to the general public without remuneration.” (Recital 74), as is the case of certain modalities of public open licensing.

In short, CHIs that negotiated agreements with authors and performers may have to provide thorough reports on the exploitation of the licensed works periodically – however, according to Article 19(3), if the administrative burden resulting from this obligation becomes disproportionate “in the light of the revenues generated by the exploitation of the work or performance”, then that obligation is merely limited to the type and level of information that can be reasonably expected.

6.2.3. – Contract adjustment mechanism (Article 20)

Information acquired through transparent reporting may lead to the conclusion that the economic value of the rights is significantly higher than initially estimated. As such, according to Article 20, and in the absence of a collective bargaining agreement that achieves the same result, authors, and performers (or their representatives), can claim additional, appropriate, and fair remuneration from a party with whom they have negotiated a licensing or transfer of exploitation rights agreement.

¹⁴² Eleonora Rosati, *Copyright in the Digital Single Market Article-by-Article Commentary to the Provisions of Directive 2019/790* (Oxford University Press 2021) 363.

The practical consequence of this provision lies on the fact that institutions may need to be prepared to adjust contracts when the original revenue or fee is shown to be disproportionately low compared to the relevant revenues derived from the subsequent exploitation of the work. This adjustment according should “take account of the specific circumstances of each case, including the contribution of the author or performer, as well as of the specificities and remuneration practices in the different content sectors” (Recital 78).

6.2.4. – Right of revocation (Article 22)

The mechanisms insofar described allow the author or performer to negotiate fair licensing terms, request information on exploitation, and adjust the contract after reassessing the economic value of the licensed asset. However, it may be the case that the licensee is not making use of the work, in which case, and according to Recital 80, “after a reasonable period of time has elapsed, authors and performers should be able to benefit from a mechanism for the revocation of rights allowing them to transfer or license their rights to another person.”. Article 22 enacts this mechanism and protects the expectations of licensees by establishing that this revocation mechanism “may only be exercised after a reasonable time following the conclusion of the licence or the transfer of the rights.” – after the expiry of that deadline, authors and performers may choose not to revoke the license, but to simply terminate the exclusivity.

In summary, CHIs should be aware of the active exploitation of the works in their collections, but rest assured that, as is the case in other mechanisms, the specificities of the different sectors and the different types of works and performances are taken into consideration¹⁴³ – as such, archival activity, restoration, and curation should fall into the scope of the normal activities of the sector¹⁴⁴ and not allow for this mechanism to be activated unless lack of use is apparent and predominant.

Application of the Evaluative Matrix to Chapter 3 of Title IV of the DSM Directive:

i) Cultural diversity:

The measures introduced in this Chapter, may and should be perceived as protective of authors and performers: the new provisions are targeted at assuring fair remuneration, transparency, and proper use of their works.

However, and very importantly, a protection and defence of the authors’ rights to fair conditions and treatment of their work does not necessarily come in direct conflict of institutions that usually rely on exceptions to use their works – a beneficiary is not necessarily and antagonist. In the case of Chapter 3 of Title IV of DSM Directive, a “silver lining” for cultural diversity can be found in the protection of the interests of rightsholders: fair remuneration for newly licensed works or through contractual adjustment mechanisms provides the rightsholder with payment that is not only

¹⁴³ European Copyright Society, Comment of the ECS on Arts. 18 to 22 DSM-D, 11 (2020) JIPITEC 132, para 71 <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3695935>> accessed 13 November 2022.

¹⁴⁴ European Copyright Society, Comment of the ECS on Arts. 18 to 22 DSM-D, 11 (2020) JIPITEC 132, para 71 <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3695935>> accessed 13 November 2022.

proportional to their work, but to its success – such measures may be perceived as creating better conditions for cultural creation within Europe.

Likewise, the possibility to revoke or retract exclusivity from a licensing agreement can possibly assure that works are used and not just held, allowing for greater dissemination of culture.

Unexpectedly, the measures devised to protect the position of authors and performers, increase their bargaining power, and generate revenue, may be beneficial for cultural diversity in Europe – after all, it is them who create culture, and better conditions benefit every interested party.

ii) Adaptation to the cross-border environment:

The measures introduced in this Chapter do not seem to have any effect on the expansion of copyright rules to the online setting, or on the dilution of barriers in the flow of content between Member States. In fact, as highlighted by the Comment of the European Copyright Society Addressing Selected Aspects of the Implementation of Articles 18 to 22 of the Directive (EU) 2019/790 on Copyright in the Digital Single Market, “It is notable that the whole section on contractual protection is not tied to any consideration of the digital environment. This is in stark contrast with the other parts of the Directive that regulate, in one way or another, issues relevant to the digital market (...)”¹⁴⁵.

iii) Legal certainty regarding technological developments:

Articles 18 to 23 do not address any new technological development or attempt to mitigate legal uncertainties associated with said technological development.

iv) Cultural creative reuse:

The provisions do not seem to have a significant impact in the enablement of cultural creative reuse.

At best, the possibility to revoke an agreement for lack of proper use may at least unlock that work and allow the author to release it to the public, if he so desires – something they would not be able to do if the work was subject to exclusivity.

v) Balance of rights:

As mentioned in the assessment of the impact on cultural diversity, the provisions of this Chapter are directly linked to the interests of authors and performers, sometimes in detriment of the other licensing party, which may be a cultural heritage institution.

¹⁴⁵ European Copyright Society, Comment of the ECS on Arts. 18 to 22 DSM-D, 11 (2020) JIPITEC 132, para 26 <<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3695935>> accessed 13 November 2022.

6.3. – Final assessment of Title IV of the DSM Directive

Chapter 6 – Title IV						
	Fostering Cultural Diversity	Adaptation to the digital environment	Suppressing technological uncertainties	Enabling creative reuse	Fair balance of interests	General evaluation of the Article(s) (CHI – centred)
Sub-Chapter 6.1 – Chapters 1 and 2 (Articles 15 to 17) [Not included in Evaluative Assessment]						
Sub-Chapter 6.2 – Chapter 3 (Articles 18 to 23)						
6.2.1 - Appropriate Remuneration (18)	+	-	-	-	0	
6.2.2 – Transparency Obligation (19)	0	-	-	-	-	
6.2.3 - Contract Adjustment (20)	+	-	-	-	+	
6.2.4 - Right of Revocation (22)	0	-	-	+	+	
Assessment of Title IV Chapter 3:	+	-	-	0	-	0

Table 4 – Final assessment of Title IV of the DSM Directive.

Note: *Green* means “Positive”; *Orange* means “Neutral” or “N/A”; *Red* means “Negative”. Overall assessment (darker shading) is performed based on the average classification of selected elements. In case of a tie or 1-point difference, priority is given to a positive assessment to avoid negative bias. Subtitles (+; 0, -) added for accessibility purposes.

7 Conclusion

Deliverable 2.4 provided a comprehensive assessment of provisions from the DSM Directive that have relevance for the activities of CHIs. This assessment was conducted in reliance on the Evaluative Matrix, which is composed of three core criteria extracted from the EU's Policy Objectives, and two additional criteria: the reuse of works and the balance of interests. Altogether, the framework of the Evaluative Matrix, applied to the relevant provisions of Titles II to IV of the DSM Directive yielded extremely varied and diverse results.

Chapter 4 of the present document focuses on Title II of the DSM Directive, introducing new mandatory exceptions and limitations. The overarching conclusions of this chapter are that, while certainly valuable for and welcome on the EU copyright framework, Articles 3 (on text and data mining) and 5 (on cross-border digital education) do not necessarily contribute to the development of and accessibility to cultural diversity. Inversely, Articles 6 and 7, on the preservation of cultural heritage, can be claimed to contribute positively to the development of cultural diversity. The relevance of the provisions of Title II for the adaptation of the copyright framework to the digital environment, and for the suppression of technological uncertainties is inconsistent, at most, with an equal number of positive and negative results stemming from the analysis. Conversely, the results from the application of the "reuse" and "fair balance" criteria were rather consistent, although not necessarily positive: Title II was shown to have zero to negative impact on cultural reuse, but to have positively established a balance of interests.

Overall, the new exceptions and limitations introduced in Title II of the DSM Directive can be said to be hardly impacting on cultural diversity (except for Article 6, and, instrumentally, Article 7) or the reuse of works, inconsistent when it comes to adapting to the digital environment and suppressing uncertainties associated with new technologies, but fairly balanced when it comes to the different interests at stake.

Regarding the new measures to improve licensing practices and ensure wider access to content introduced in Title III and analysed in Chapter 5 of the document, the results are overall positive. Both Articles 8 and 14 were considered to provide an adequate framework to promote and disseminate cultural diversity, as well as to establish a fair balance of interests. Conversely, neither was considered to adequately provide for a sufficient level of legal certainty. Finally, while Article 14 was considered to effectively adapt the copyright framework to the digital environment, and, notably, to promote and enable transformative uses and reuse, Article 8's impact on those two fields left much to be desired.

At last, the provisions on Chapter 3 of Title IV, on fair remuneration in exploitation contracts of authors and performers was considered to have neutral to negative impact on the cultural sector. It was argued that all of the provisions somewhat contributed to cultural diversity by providing a safer, stabler and more balanced framework for artists to navigate, but in general disregard of the remaining objectives or criteria.

In conclusion, this study argues that new mandatory provisions are more than welcome and generally well-rounded, generally envisioning cultural heritage institutions as beneficiaries albeit not

necessarily working strictly in their benefit. These provisions should not be limited by strict definitions, optional carve-outs (such as the licensing priorities in Article 5), restrictive obligations for the beneficiaries (such as secure storage obligations in Article 3) or by compensation for their use, and that these exceptions are well complemented by safeguards such as contractual and technological override, but the introduction of such concepts should be accompanied by actual complaint, redress and removal mechanisms to make them usable and efficient. It is also argued that the new provisions impacting licensing and access to content are overall positive, with minor pitfalls, such as uncertainties regarding core concepts such as sufficient representativity of CMOs, or the relationship between the Directive and other instruments such as the PSI Directive. The provisions on fair remuneration and contracts for authors and performers were lacking in their disregard for the digital environment and for creating an added layer of uncertainty to cultural heritage institutions.

Overall, the contribution of the Directive for the cultural sector is positive but with a lot of reservations: new mandatory exceptions for necessary uses, such as preservation, complement digitization tasks effectively but may not be the field with the most pressing need for harmonization; new licensing schemes for out-of-commerce works allow cultural heritage institutions to make works available to the public, but in heavy dependence on the efficient support of nationally-appointed bodies; new provisions on fair remuneration are drafted in benefit of authors and performers, and allow them more stability, but possibly in detriment of the positions of cultural heritage institutions.

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